

Climate health risks to children and adolescents: exposures, policy and practice interventions

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2 Executive summary

Health issues

Children and adolescents are especially vulnerable to climate change due to their developing bodies and immune systems (Anderko et al., 2020). Extreme heat affects them more severely, making them more susceptible to dehydration, heat exhaustion, and heatstroke (Vanos et al., 2017). Poorly ventilated, overcrowded classrooms further hinder their ability to concentrate and perform (Salthammer et al., 2016). Prenatal stress can also lead to preterm birth, low birth weight, and developmental issues (King et al., 2012).

Children's faster breathing rates mean they inhale more pollutants, increasing their risk of respiratory diseases, asthma, and eczema, particularly when combined with high temperatures (Pinkerton and Joad, 2000; Huss-Marp et al., 2006). Their outdoor activities expose them to more UV radiation, pollutants, and disease vectors. Behaviors like playing on the ground and mouthing objects increase their contact with contaminants. Natural disasters make them more prone to injuries, malnutrition, and food- and waterborne diseases.

Climate change also affects children's mental health, causing fear and distress from witnessing extreme events, school closures, and displacement. "Eco-anxiety" from environmental destruction and uncertainty about the future harms their mental health and academic performance (Léger-Goodes et al., 2022). Their reliance on adults limits their ability to protect themselves during climate-related events (Sanson et al., 2022). After disasters, children may adopt unhealthy behaviors, such as academic disengagement, poor eating habits, substance abuse, and smoking (Manning and Clayton, 2018; Hoey et al., 2020).

Observed effects

In recent decades, children and adolescents across Europe have increasingly suffered health impacts linked to climate change. Heatwaves have led to dehydration, heatstroke, and worsened respiratory disorders. One in two children in Europe now faces 4-5 heatwaves annually (UNICEF, 2023). Nearly half of schools in European cities are in urban heat islands, where temperatures are at least 2°C higher than regional averages (European Climate and Health Observatory, 2022). Heatwaves have increased emergency hospital admissions for cardiovascular, respiratory, and renal diseases among children (Xu et al., 2014), with 52 heatstroke-related child deaths recorded in the UK in 2018 (Forsyth & Solan, 2022).

Increased flooding heightens children's risk of casualties, waterborne diseases, and mental health issues (EEA, 2024). Approximately one in ten schools in Europe is located in flood-prone areas (European Climate and Health Observatory, 2022), and playing in dry floodplains has led to parasitic infections (Gertler et al., 2015). Poor air quality, worsened by wildfires and heatwaves, has exacerbated respiratory conditions like asthma. From 2010 to 2019, air pollution contributed to 5,839 infant deaths in Europe (UNICEF, 2024), and one-third of childhood asthma cases are attributed to air pollution (Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2023). Rising pollen levels due to warming have also increased allergy-related health issues (Beck et al., 2013).

Climate change has shifted the distribution of infectious diseases in Europe. Warmer climates have expanded habitats for ticks, mosquitoes, and other vectors, increasing cases of Lyme disease, tick-borne encephalitis, and mosquito-borne diseases such as dengue and West Nile Fever, even in areas previously considered low-risk (Semenza and Suk, 2018). Children, with their less developed immune systems, are at greater risk of severe outcomes.

Changes in precipitation and extreme weather have led to crop failures in parts of Europe. Although trade mitigates food shortages, higher prices reduce access to healthy food, affecting children's nutrition, cognitive development, and overall health (EEA, 2024).

Psychologically, European youth are increasingly affected by climate anxiety. Over 50% report feeling anxious, angry, or powerless, with over 30% stating these feelings impact their daily life and ability to function (Hickman et al., 2021).

Projected effects

As climate change continues, health risks for children and adolescents are expected to rise. Injuries, fatalities, and mental health issues related to extreme weather events, such as heatwaves, storms, and floods, will likely increase (Amengual et al., 2014). Children born in 2020 in Europe will experience about four times more extreme events, especially heatwaves, than those born in 1960 (Thiery et al., 2021). By 2050, all European children will face 4-5 heatwaves per year, along with the associated health risks (UNICEF, 2023). Respiratory diseases will worsen due to longer, more intense pollen seasons (Rasmussen et al., 2017). Vector-borne diseases, such as those spread by mosquitoes and ticks, will become more common in previously unaffected areas (Semenza and Suk, 2018). Changes in weather patterns will also increase risks of water- and foodborne diseases and malnutrition due to impacts on water quality and food production (Semenza et al., 2017; EEA, 2024). Young people will face higher risks of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress, exacerbated by climate change-related displacement, community destruction, loss of loved ones, education disruptions, and social instability (Clayton et al., 2023).

Policy responses

Reducing climate-related health risks for children requires urgent, child-focused adaptation of healthcare and support systems. In 2022, the Council of the European Union adopted a Recommendation on learning for the green transition. EU-funded projects like OASIS and myBUILDINGisGREEN focus on creating cool islands in schools and playgrounds to mitigate heat impacts. Projects like SINPHONIE have provided recommendations and technological solutions to reduce air pollution in schools.

Awareness is key in disaster risk reduction. Projects such as WATERCARE and Hull Children's Flood raise awareness about flooding and water quality through educational modules and hands-on labs. Tools to educate children include a toolkit on vector-borne diseases by the ECDC and a Dutch educational game on ticks and Lyme disease.

Vaccination is a highly effective defence against tick-borne encephalitis (TBE), but recommendations for children vary across Europe. Austria and Switzerland have national vaccination programs, while other countries base recommendations on risk factors (Steffen, 2019; Erber and Schmitt, 2018).

Figure 1: Major aspects of exposure, vulnerability, and resulting health risks for children and youth due to climate change

3 Introduction

Climate change poses significant challenges to the health and well-being of populations worldwide, and Europe is no exception. Originating primarily from anthropogenic activities such as industrialization, transportation, residential sector, and agriculture, the emission of greenhouse gases has led to unprecedented alterations in Earth's climate systems⁽¹⁾. These changes manifest in various forms, including rising temperatures, shifting precipitation patterns, more frequent and intense extreme weather events, such as heat waves, heavy rainfall, floods, droughts, forest fires, storms also a shift in vector spread, impacting ecosystems, economies, and human health across the continent (Helldén et al., 2021).

Children and adolescents in Europe face direct and indirect health effects from climate change. Direct impacts of climate change encompass shifts in temperatures, such as heat waves and more rapidly fluctuating temperatures, as well as altered precipitation patterns leading to a heightened risk of floods, droughts, and wildfires. Indirect effects extend to ecosystem disruption, altered vector patterns, increased air pollution, and more prevalent aeroallergens. Child health risks due to these effects include a spectrum of health risks, including heat-related illnesses, respiratory ailments from air pollution, injuries from extreme weather events such as floods and storms, and increased exposure to allergens and infectious diseases. (Hellden et al. 2021; Rocque et al., 2021).

Climate change plays a multiplier role, amplifying existing health risks and worsening children's health problems through different pathways (Figure 2) (Kjellstrom & McMichael, 2015).

Rising global temperatures, attributed to climate change, lead to increased **air pollution** through longer summers and shorter winters (Arnell et al., 2019; Hodgson & Phillips, 2021). This heightened pollution includes ground-level ozone, formed in warm weather from various sources such as microbial growth and agricultural activities (Fiala et al., 2003; Ren et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2021).

⁽¹⁾ Retrieved on 23/05/2024 from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=File:Greenhouse_gas_emissions_Dec2023_1920px.jpg

Additionally, warmer temperatures trap pollutants near the ground, forming smog, especially in urban areas (Jacob & Winner, 2009). Thawing **permafrost** due to climate change releases stored mercury, contributing to environmental contamination and bioaccumulation in organisms (Schaefer et al., 2020; Schuster et al., 2018). Early **pollen** seasons and prolonged pollen exposure exacerbate respiratory diseases and allergies, further linked to climate change-induced shifts in vegetation distribution (Beck et al., 2013; Rojo et al., 2021; Silverberg et al., 2015; El Kelish et al., 2014; Jato et al., 2013; Wayne et al., 2002).

Temperature and humidity significantly affect environmental conditions, plant and insect distribution, affecting vectors like mosquitoes and ticks and pathogen reservoir hosts like rodents and birds. With climate change, European regions may witness warmer temperatures, favoring the spread of vector species and leading to the northward expansion of **vector-borne diseases**. Alterations in seasonal patterns can influence vector activity and pathogen development, potentially increasing disease transmission opportunities. Moreover, changing climates may introduce new vector species, posing risks to populations lacking immunity to emerging diseases (Fischer et al., 2010; Semenza & Suk, 2018).

Climate change leads to more frequent and intense **extreme weather events** (Weilhammer et al., 2021), including heavy rainfall, high temperatures, wildfires, heat waves, droughts, floods, and storms. Wildfire smoke, rich in particulate matter and carbon monoxide, worsens air quality and respiratory health (De Sario et al., 2013; Holm et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2015). Droughts exacerbate **waterborne diseases** due to reduced dilution of pollutants (Bryan et al., 2020; Stanke et al., 2013), while water scarcity prompts the use of untreated alternative sources, compromising water quality (Al Aukidy & Verlicchi, 2017). Floods overwhelm sewage systems, leading to contamination and increased cases of diarrheal diseases (Lehmkuhl et al., 2022). These events also cause property damage, economic losses, injuries, and fatalities, negatively affecting mental health (Dyregrov et al., 2018; Kirch et al., 2005; Lane et al., 2013; Paterson et al., 2018).

Geographical features in cities, like the **Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect**, exacerbate climate change impacts by raising urban air temperatures through the amount of green spaces, density of buildings, roadways, and how the city is ventilated⁽²⁾. Extreme heat increases the risk of e.g cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, and respiratory diseases, while amplifying air pollution (Ward et al., 2016). Stagnant water in heated urban areas fosters mosquito breeding, aiding disease spread, and warms nearby water bodies, heightening waterborne disease risks (Mathieu & Kamali, 2016; Cruz-Paredes et al., 2021).

Climate change can induce socio-economic shifts, potentially leading to social instability and adverse health outcomes (Sanson et al., 2022). Rising energy prices, driven by a shift to renewable energy sources, may result in **fuel poverty**, leading to cold-related illnesses (Charlier & Legendre, 2021; Thomson & Snell, 2013). Agricultural challenges arise from shifts in temperature and precipitation patterns, impacting food production, distribution, and access. Extreme weather events can damage crops, disrupt supply chains, and create conditions favorable for pests and diseases, contributing to **food insecurity** (Fujimori et al., 2019; Godde et al., 2021). Additionally, extreme weather may disrupt schooling, impairing children's physical health and access to education (Sanson et al., 2022).

⁽²⁾ Retrieved on 23/05/2024 from <https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/urban/urban-heat-island> and <https://www.meteoswiss.admin.ch/weather/weather-and-climate-from-a-to-z/urban-heat-island-effect.html>

Figure 2: Climate change and child health: an expanded framework

Note: The dashed lines show where mitigation and adaptation can reduce the effects of climate change on child health and wellbeing. HFMD=Hand, foot, and mouth diseases.

Source: adapted from Helldén et al., 2021.

From the escalating frequency and severity of extreme weather events to the insidious consequences of air pollution, pollen, vector-borne diseases (Patz and Reisen, 2001), food- and water-borne diseases and food insecurity, the health vulnerabilities of this demographic group are multifaceted (Donat et al., 2013; Fischer & Knutti, 2014; Noyes et al., 2009; El Kelish et al., 2014; Rahaman et al., 2020; Poursafa & Kelishadi, 2011; Helldén et al., 2021). Children and adolescents are uniquely vulnerable to the health impacts of climate change due to physiological and behavioral factors. They have higher respiratory rates (Salvi, 2007), immature immune systems (Bunyavanich et al., 2003), and a greater skin surface area relative to body weight, increasing their susceptibility to heat stress, air pollution, and vector-borne diseases. Their higher activity levels and more time spent outdoors lead to greater exposure (Xu et al., 2014), and hand-to-mouth activities heighten the risk of fecal-oral infections. Limited coping mechanisms and physical abilities make them more vulnerable during extreme weather events (Ngure et al., 2019). Additionally, children lack the resources to independently cope with climate challenges, relying on caregivers and societal structures for support (Atazadeh et al., 2022). As previously mentioned, children manage high temperatures differently from adults, mainly due to differences in their body proportions and heat loss mechanisms compared to fully mature individuals. Physical fitness directly affects heat tolerance, but children today are less fit and more obese than in the past. Consequently, as the planet's climate and weather patterns grow increasingly extreme, children may become less able to cope with these conditions (Morrison, 2023).

This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the direct and indirect effects of climate change on the health of children and adolescents in Europe, synthesizing current research findings. Furthermore, we review practical interventions, exploring concrete initiatives aimed at mitigating climate-related health risks for children and adolescents. Whether nature-based and technical solutions or educational programs, our aim is to present interventions for the target population. The focus will be on strategies implemented in child-centered environments, such as schools, kindergartens, or playgrounds.

4 Methodology

We have outlined five areas of exposure related to climate change: a) Extreme weather events (extreme heat, storms, heavy precipitation, floods, droughts, water scarcity, and wildfires); b) Pollen (allergic reactions) and air pollution; c) Arthropod vectors (ticks, mosquitoes, and sandflies); d) Food- and water-borne diseases pathogens e) Food insecurity. To comprehensively investigate these areas, we conducted two types of reviews for each of these five domains. Firstly, we conducted a systematic review aimed to identify key environmental health risks topics by formulating a literature research strategy. Secondly, we carried out an umbrella review by relying on secondary literature that summarizes primary research findings. This secondary literature includes systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and reports from authoritative sources like the US Environmental Protection Agency or UN reports. In case, identified secondary literature indicated valuable primary research, we supplemented this collection of literature with single studies tailored to the European context. Additionally, existing interventions, studies, policies and programs throughout Europe to reduce the exposure of children and adolescents to climate risks and their impacts on health were analyzed in a scoping review. The steps followed in the systematic review to identify key topics, the umbrella review to summarize health effects on children and adolescents related to climate change and the scoping review compiling research about intervention strategies to reduce these outcomes are described in the chapters below.

4.1 Systematic Review

Aim

The primary objective of the systematic review is to pinpoint the most important environmental health risks by conducting a comprehensive synthesis of the existing scientific evidence regarding the impact of climate-related exposures on the health of children and adolescents within the European context. Additionally, the summarized evidence will be categorized according to climate risk and the geographical area of exposure, whenever this information is available.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The databases PubMed, and Google Scholar were searched. Both peer-reviewed publications and grey literature. Geographically, it will encompass the 32 member countries of the European Environment Agency (EEA) and 6 collaborating countries. The systematic review will focus on exposures that may occur in various settings such as schools, daycare facilities, and nurseries' home environments and outdoor settings. Only studies written in the English language will be considered and published from 2000 January 1 to 2023 December 1 were considered.

General approach

To ensure a structured and systematic approach, the PECO/PICO framework (Population, Exposure/Intervention, Comparison, Outcome) was employed to select topics for inclusion in this review.

Population: Articles were considered if they reported on children aged 0-18 years, in accordance with the age definition outlined in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. This includes age groups such as new-born (<1 month), infants (<1 year), children (1-12 years) and adolescents (12-18 years). Perinatal period was also included.

Comparator: For each of the five mentioned exposure categories, specific search terms were defined to ensure that the included literature sufficiently covered the topic as much as possible. As an example, different types of extreme weather phenomena were included in the list of search terms in the *extreme weather* category.

Outcomes: The numerous health effects on children and adolescents related to climatic factors.

Many environmental exposures can impact the health of children and adolescents, but research in some of these areas is limited, resulting in constrained evidence for assessing risks. Conversely, certain exposures may not be deemed high priority, though they cannot be dismissed entirely. Therefore, a prioritization process is established based on the following criteria:

- The availability of existing research and evidence
- The potential effects on the health of the overall population
- Consideration of whether the exposure is specifically applicable to children in the European context.

Literature search

Search terms

A comprehensive search strategy was devised for identifying relevant articles, with a focus on the PubMed database. The R package easyPubMed was used to compile the literature. The basic structure of the search query as designed for each climatic exposure category was *term 1* AND *term 2* AND *term 3* AND *term 4*, whereby the terms related to the following:

- *Term 1:* Search terms to capture climate-related exposure for one out of the five selected exposure categories
- *Term 2:* Key terms for research climate change-related research: “climate change” OR “global warming”
- *Term 3:* Search term to define the target population: “child*” OR “adolescent*”
- *Term 4:* Search terms to limit the study design: “review” OR “meta anal*” OR “meta-anal*”

While *term 1* was a different combination of search terms depending on the researched climatic exposure category, *term 2, 3* and *4* remained the same in all five search queries (see Appendix A, table A.1).

Important risk factors included

The search terms of the five categories of climatic exposures were further refined by analyzing previously published literature also aiming at collecting evidence about climate change and health by using the search engines PubMed, and Google Scholar. The following table displays the search terms included for each category.

Table 1: Search terms for the systematic review

Climate Exposures	Search Terms
Extreme Weather	“extreme weather” OR “extreme heat” OR “heavy precipitation” OR “extreme rain” OR “flood*” OR “drought*” OR “water scarcity” OR “wildfire*”
Pollen and air pollution	“pollen” OR “ air pollution”
Arthropod vectors	“vector-borne*” OR “vectorborne*” OR “vector borne*” OR “arthropod*” OR “arthropod vector” OR “tick*” OR “mosquito*” OR “sandfly” OR “sandflies”
Food- and water-borne diseases pathogens	“food-borne disease*” OR food-borne pathogen*” OR “water-borne disease*” OR “water-borne pathogen*”
Food insecurity	“food insecurity”

Health effects included

By conducting a quantitative assessment of the found literature, key health effects were identified as a result of different climatic exposures. A list of all found health effects categorized by climatic exposure category can be found in appendix I.

4.2 Umbrella review

Aim

The aim of the umbrella review is to summarize selected evidence on the health of children and adolescents in Europe with respect to environmental risks. The purpose idea of the subsequent umbrella review is to summarize the systematic review's findings. However, for climatic exposures with only a few selected studies, primary literature of high quality, such as prospective cohort studies with high quality exposure and outcome assessment will also be considered.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The PubMed and Google Scholar databases, and reports published on official websites were used for literature search. Evidence from literature published between 2000 January 1 to 2024 March 1 was selected. Official reports, grey literature, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses were included. Research published within the 32 member countries of the European Environment Agency (EEA) and 6 collaborating countries was prioritized. However, in case of information scarcity the search was extended beyond Europe. The search was restricted to the English language.

Literature search

Additionally to the already described search strategy, we search the health effects found in the systematic review for reports on official websites.

Literature selection

Literature prioritized in the ETC-HE works from 2022 was once again included in the literature selection of this umbrella review:

- Compendium of World Health Organization (WHO) and other United Nations (UN) guidance on health and environment (WHO, 2021)
- The Lancet Commission on pollution and health (Landrigan et al., 2018)
- Environmental Burden of Childhood Disease in Europe (Rojas-Rueda et al., 2019)

Furthermore, a strong focus was placed on the information portrayed on the following websites:

- World Health Organization (<https://www.who.int/teams/environment-climate-change-and-health/settings-and-populations/children>)
- European Climate and Health Observatory Lancet Countdown Europe (<https://www.lancetcountdown.org/europe/>)
-
- UN Environment Programme (<https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/press-release/enhancing-childrens-rights-safe-climate-clean-air-and-healthy>)
- United States Environmental Protection Agency ([https://www.epa.gov/climateimpacts/climate-change-and-childrens-health#:~:text=Climate%20change%20may%20affect%20certain,organisms%20in%20the%20food%20chain.&text=For%20instance%2C%20Escherichia%20coli%20\(E,warmer%20and%20more%20humid%20climate.&text=These%20climate%20changes%2C%20combined%20with,to%20some%20food-related%20illnesses.\)](https://www.epa.gov/climateimpacts/climate-change-and-childrens-health#:~:text=Climate%20change%20may%20affect%20certain,organisms%20in%20the%20food%20chain.&text=For%20instance%2C%20Escherichia%20coli%20(E,warmer%20and%20more%20humid%20climate.&text=These%20climate%20changes%2C%20combined%20with,to%20some%20food-related%20illnesses.)))

The following reports and secondary literature were relied on:

- A scoping review about climate change and child health, *The Lancet*, (Helldén et al., 2021)
- Report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change analysing implications for the mental health policy of children and adolescents in Europe in a scoping review (Clemens et al., 2020)
- A scoping review of risk and protective factors about climate change impacts on the mental health and wellbeing of young people: A scoping review of risk and protective factors (Ma et al., 2022)
- Progress in understanding climate change's effects on children and youth (Brodie & Silberholz, 2021)
- Climate change and state of the science for children's health and environmental health equity (Fuller et al., 2022)
- A review of risks, exposures, and impacts related to climate changes reproductive and children's health (Anderko et al., 2020)
- A review on strategies of prevention about climate change and children's health (Perry & Landigran, 2011)

For specific main areas of research, we have further considered additional key reports for the selection of relevant outcomes and exposure conditions as listed in the references

4.3 Scoping review of interventions/policies

Aim

The final scoping review aims to compile the interventions, policies and prevention programs in place throughout Europe to reduce the exposure of children and adolescents to climate risks and their health impacts. The variety and efficiency of interventions to reduce climate risk exposure of children and adolescents in the general population will be examined. Additionally, key regulations, policies, and stakeholders at the EU level and their impact on reducing climate risks to child and adolescent health in Europe will be geographically mapped.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The type of study will not be limited to the search of intervention strategies, policies and prevention programs. PubMed, Google Scholar, and official websites listed above will be used as a search engine. Once again, the search will be limited to the English language and the time frame between 2000 January 1 to 2024 March 1. Only intervention and policies within Europe, targeting specifically children and adolescents, and with published results will be considered.

General approach

We treat intervention studies as a distinct category of evidence generation, as they can directly suggest solutions for improving the situation. Within the scoping review, we give attention to intervention topics that hold significant relevance for the health of children and adolescents. We delve into intervention research related to the exposures previously identified as relevant in the systematic review and subjected to prioritization. The scoping review encompasses intervention studies and reviews that have evaluated interventions addressing the five exposures. For each type of intervention, we identify the health outcomes, as well as the published evidence supporting these interventions.

Literature selection

Interventions were searched using the PubMed and Google Scholar databases, as well as grey literature and reports published from official websites. The following articles were prioritized in the scoping review about interventions and policies aiming to reduce health effects resulting from climate-related exposures:

- Multilevel interventions as climate change adaptation response to protect maternal and child health: a scoping review protocol
- 897 Impact on child health of climate change mitigation policies: a systematic review, Climate Change Working Group, 2022
- A literature review of child-centered climate change adaptation approaches (Treichel, 2020)

5 Impacts of climate change on children and adolescent health

5.1 Children's Vulnerability

Children are particularly susceptible to the negative health effects of climate change due to several factors:

- 1. Physiological Vulnerability:** Children's bodies are still developing, and their physiological systems may not be as robust as those of adults (Anderko et al., 2020). A higher ratio of body surface area to body mass promotes a greater transfer of temperature with their environment, ultimately making the body temperature of a child more responsive to the surrounding climate (Vanos et al., 2017). Also, their elevated metabolic rate reduces cardiac output compared to adults during similar activity levels. This effect is especially pronounced in younger children, impacting their ability to physically adapt to changing climatic conditions (Bunyavanich et al., 2003). Children typically have smaller body volumes compared to adults, and overall produce less sweat, which limits their potential to dissipate heat to their surroundings to cool down (Forsyth & Solan, 2022). Children breathe more rapidly and have a higher water intake proportional to their body weights than adults (D'Anci et al., 2006; Salvi et al., 2007). The skin of children is more susceptible to sunburns compared to adult skin (Bunyavanich et al., 2003). Children are at a higher risk of experiencing injuries and other physiological impairments during natural disasters compared to adults (Biswas et al., 2010). Finally, the longer life expectancy of children means that they are exposed to extreme heat for an extended duration, providing more time for delayed health effects to manifest (Xu et al., 2014).
- 2. Immaturity of Immune Systems:** Children generally have less-developed immune systems compared to adults, making them more prone to infections and diseases (Bunyavanich et al., 2003).
- 3. Higher susceptibility due to behavior:** Children are more active compared to adults, typically spend more time outdoors exposed to the environment and engage in more strenuous activities. All these factors increase their vulnerability to health effects caused by heat or air pollution, both intensified by climate change (Xu et al., 2014). Furthermore, children tend to participate in more hand-to-mouth activities putting them at a higher risk for fecal-oral infection with soil-, food- or waterborne diseases associated with environmental contamination (Ngure et al., 2019). Especially, small children may not yet have sufficient coping mechanisms or the ability to swim or run to avert the negative effects during an extreme weather event and natural disasters (Garcia et al., 2016).
- 4. Greater Dependency on Adults:** Children rely on adults for care, protection, and decision-making. They may be less able to cope with extreme weather events, such as heat waves, floods, or storms and may face challenges accessing necessary resources such as food, safe water or medicine during such events (Atazadeh et al., 2022). Furthermore, children may be more vulnerable to malnutrition and its associated health effects, particularly in low-income households (Mahapatra et al., 2021).
- 5. Psychosocial Impact:** Climate change-related events, such as natural disasters, can have psychosocial effects on children. Displacement, loss of homes, exposure to traumatic events, or disruptions in education can have lasting impacts on mental health and well-being. Disruptions in schooling can affect the access of children to essential health information and services (Dyregrov et al., 2018; Ortega Pacheco & Barrero Toncel, 2022). Additionally, children tend to show unique clinical symptoms often dissimilar from adults which can be challenging to diagnose (Vanos et al., 2017).

5.2 Extreme weather events

Across all of Europe, the frequency, and intensity of extreme weather events, such as storms, extremely high temperatures, heat waves, wildfires, droughts, extreme precipitation and floods, increases with climate change (Milliman annual report, 2022). We will define in this section how the health and wellbeing of are affected when exposed to such extreme weather events.

Storms: hurricanes, tornados, cyclones, typhoons, ice/dust storms

Exposure

Due to children's behavioral limitations and their dependency on adults as previously mentioned in chapter 5.2, children are among the most vulnerable population groups during storms. An increase in wind speed, particularly observed in the Northern part of Central Europe and southern Baltic Sea region (Andersen et al., 2001; Bengtsson et al., 2006; Donat et al., 2010), signaled a potential rise in the intensity of cyclones and storms. Nevertheless, a decrease in such events was recorded in and around Iceland and Scandinavia (Geng & Sugi, 2003; Bengtsson et al., 2006; Pinto et al., 2007). Across all of Europe during the past four to six decades, a rise in storm frequency from the 1970s to the mid-1990s due to a potential shift in the North Atlantic storm track towards the polar region and an eastward extension towards Europe has been observed (Alexandersson et al., 2000).

Observed health effects

Mental health disorders (post-traumatic stress disorders (PTSD), anxiety, depression, trauma, suicidality)

Mental health disorders are among the most prevalent consequences of natural disasters, such as storms. These conditions often arise from experiences like personal injury, the loss of loved ones, property damage, disruption to one's normal way of life, and the impediment of livelihoods in the aftermath of a disaster (Manning & Clayton, 2018). Children, in particular, are susceptible to psychological trauma due to their ongoing development of coping mechanisms, leading to issues like anxiety, depression, bipolar disorder, and interpersonal aggression (Mambrey et al., 2019). Research suggests that immediately after a disaster, acute traumatic stress, similar to post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) but of shorter duration, is the most common mental health concern. This is typically accompanied by anxiety, depression, and substance abuse (Fritze et al., 2008). Moreover, the effects of PTSD, depression, general anxiety, and even suicide can persist for months or years following a disaster. In addition, more significant mental health effects have been found in adolescents compared to children. First of all, mental impairment in young individuals was more likely to be chronic with long-lasting symptoms. Also, it was found that children usually do not put in the effort to achieve mental recovery leading to delayed stress due to lack of coping and negative impacts from traumatic events gradually worsening over time (Weems & Banks, 2015). Additionally, a common pathway leading to mental health disorders is the initial experience of solastalgia, or eco-anxiety, which is a sense of unease resulting from environmental changes. Research indicates that children undergo emotional reactions and eco-anxiety upon becoming aware of climate change, and the increasingly frequent extreme weather events. This can result in mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, as well as intense emotions like sorrow, frustration, and apprehension (Léger-Goodes et al., 2022).

Behavioral disorders (smoking, substance abuse, unhealthy eating habits)

In the aftermath of disasters, people are more prone to many behaviors that may negatively impact overall health such as smoking, risk-taking, and unhealthy eating habits (Manning & Clayton, 2018). Children are especially prone to the negative effects of such behavioral disorders, due to them having a much more long-lasting impact on their lives. Most important for children are behaviors such as academic failure and substance abuse (Bryan et al., 2020; Hoey et al., 2020).

Injuries

During extreme storms, there is an increased likelihood of acute physical trauma, such as being struck by debris or by building collapse, increase of traffic accidents, people may sustain nonfatal injuries such as cuts or broken bones (Manning & Clayton, 2009). There is an increased danger of being injured by falling trees. In 2022, at least three children are dead in Italy, Austria, and on the French island of Corsica, because of an extreme storm⁽³⁾.

Projected effects

The findings of several studies suggest a high risk of more intense storms with the continuation of current climate change scenarios, particularly for the British Isles, the North Sea, and the northwestern part of Europe. However, storm intensities show a clearly increasing trend associated with anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions for all analyzed geographical regions in Europe (Feser et al., 2015; Mölter et al., 2016). This increase in storms is projected to lead to more injuries, behavioral and mental disorders (Padhy et al., 2015).

Heat exposure: extremely high temperatures, heat waves, wildfires

Exposure

Extremely high temperatures are a well-documented consequence of climate change, leading to more frequent and extended heat waves, a rise in hot days, meaning a temperature above 30°C during the day (EEA, 2023), and an increased prevalence of wildfires (European Commission, 2017). Europe has been the most affected region in terms of rise in extremely hot conditions since the 1950s, with these events occurring more frequently than in other regions. Over the past 70 years, the average number of days with extreme heat has more than tripled, with temperatures rising by 2.3°C (Donat et al., 2013; Fischer & Knutti, 2014)⁽⁴⁾. Densely populated urban areas, characterized by limited greenery and high concentrations of heat-absorbing structures, act as hotspots for extreme temperatures, exacerbating the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect (Ward et al., 2016). A mortality analysis for summer 2022 estimated 61,672 heat-related deaths, with Italy bearing the highest toll of over 18,000 heat-related deaths (Ballester et al., 2023). Such high excess mortality rates are expected to become the new norm due to the rapidly increasing temperatures in Europe. This is especially relevant for children as a vulnerable population group for heat-related health effects. As a reference, a total of 52 children died from heatstroke in the UK in 2018 and numbers are projected to increase over the next 30 years (Forsyth & Solan, 2022).

Observed health effects

The health repercussions of extreme heat are manifold. Significant associations exist between exposure to extreme heat and mortality, as well as elevated risks for cardiovascular, respiratory, renal, and mental diseases.

Acute and chronic diseases due to heat waves

Common health conditions during heat waves are dehydration, electrolyte imbalance, heat stress or heat exhaustion. High temperatures induce sweating and fluid loss, causing dehydration, which is especially concerning in children due to their smaller fluid reserves and can disrupt the balance of essential minerals and electrolytes in the body (Popkin et al., 2010). Especially, if classrooms are too small for the number of schoolchildren and/or have poor ventilation concepts, conditions may deteriorate even more during heat waves (Salthammer et al., 2016). Common symptoms such as sweating, feeling thirsty, discomfort, headache, stomach aches, prickly heat, getting easily irritated, feeling sluggish, weakness and dehydration that children experience during heat waves, negatively affect their concentration. Young population reported being concerned about their studies and

⁽³⁾ Retrieved on 12/02/2024 from <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-62598573>

⁽⁴⁾ Retrieved on 30/05/2024 from <https://climate.copernicus.eu/climate-indicators/temperature>

progress at school resulting in elevated stress levels due to heat waves (Ashraf & Faruk, et al., 2018). Furthermore, several studies show a link between school closures because of hot days and poorer mental health in children. Cancellation of classes is associated with an increase of children with emotional problems, behavioral problems, hyperactivity, anxiety and depression in several studies. Emotional instability may result from diminished social relations or disrupted health behavior routines, such as decreased physical activity (Felfe et al., 2023; Hawrilenko et al., 2021; Lehmann et al., 2022; Miao et al., 2023). Extreme heat not only induces acute health effects but also poses risks for aggravating chronic diseases, particularly in pediatric populations. Studies by Xu et al. (2014) and Kovats et al. (2004) have linked heat waves to increased emergency hospital admissions among children for cardiovascular, respiratory, and renal diseases, with those under five being particularly vulnerable. Physiological responses to heat, such as elevated core body temperature, increased heart rate, and dehydration, contribute to these health risks (Kjellström et al., 2010). Researchers underscored the correlation between temperature rise and hospitalizations for cardiovascular and respiratory ailments (Lin et al., 2009), while other meta-analyses highlight the link between heat exposure and kidney disease morbidity (Hansen et al. 2008; Lee et al. 2019).

Health effects (injuries, respiratory diseases, cardiovascular diseases, renal diseases, mental health disorders) due to wildfires

Wildfire smoke, containing high levels of small particle size particulate matter (PM), carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, as well as other air pollutants that have the potential to cause toxic effects (Dong et al., 2017). Children are a particularly vulnerable group due to their small lungs and other physiological as well as psychosocial factors as mentioned in chapter 5.2. Especially problematic is the fact that less airborne particles settle in the noses of children and a higher proportion of wildfire-related smoke can penetrate the deep layers of the lungs compared to adults. Additionally, surgical masks are usually not designed for children and therefore provide limited protection (Bennett et al., 2007; Holm et al., 2021). Wildfires have immediate and lasting health impacts. Direct exposure to flames and heat can cause burns, injuries, dehydration, and heatstroke, often fatal (Kizer, 2020; Rossiello & Szema, 2019). Inhalation of wildfire smoke can lead to chronic respiratory issues like asthma and bronchitis (Kizer, 2021; Vicedo-Cabrera et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2020) and is associated with cardiovascular diseases, psychological disorders, and higher mortality rates (Analitis et al., 2012; Desai et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2015). Traumatic experiences during wildfires, such as loss or property damage, can result in post-traumatic stress disorder, depression, and insomnia (Xu et al., 2020).

Preterm birth, perinatal period, developmental impairments due to heat-related stressors

Preterm birth is an increasingly common and debilitating condition, often resulting from prenatal maternal stress. It is frequently triggered by environmental stressors, such as high ambient temperatures, heat waves, or natural disasters. One possible explanation for this relationship is that during periods of extreme heat, the body is unable to adapt quickly enough to rapid change and is overwhelmed leading to induced labor (Carolan-Olah & Frankowska, 2014). Stress during pregnancy and preterm birth can have negative effects on the fetus and consequently impact the infant's cognitive, physical, motoric, behavioral, reproductive, emotional, social, neurological, skeletal health lead to negative pediatric health outcomes such as low birth weight, impaired cognitive, behavioral, and motor development (King et al., 2012). During the perinatal period, mortality for infants under one year of age increased by 25% on hot days. The increased risk was mainly due to conditions originating in the perinatal period, with mortality risk increasing on extremely hot days. The specific causes driving this high risk included disorders of the digestive system, hemorrhagic and hematologic disorders, infections, and cardiovascular and respiratory causes (Basagaña et al., 2011).

Projected effects

Central Europe is projected to warm by 1°C to over 4°C in the next 50 to 80 years, depending on emissions scenarios (Hertig et al., 2023). Heat waves in Europe are expected to intensify, become

more frequent, and last longer. They are projected to extend into Northern Europe, with a 7°C increase in amplitude. Mediterranean countries could see average daily temperatures rise by over 2°C by 2075, with coastal and low-altitude regions most vulnerable (Amengual et al., 2014). This will have severe health implications, especially in Southern Europe and the Mediterranean (Fischer & Schär, 2010). There is likely an increase in children experiencing heatstroke, a perilous condition, particularly risky for infants. In severe scenarios, it may lead to organ failure. Additionally, prolonged exposure to heat can contribute to various health issues among children such as heightened instances of asthma, allergies, cardiovascular ailments, and respiratory issues. Furthermore, during heat waves, children may face challenges in maintaining concentration, potentially affecting their educational performance (Scheffel, 2023 (UNICEF)). Children born in 2020 are projected to encounter a substantial rise in extreme occurrences, particularly heat waves, compared to those born in 1960, by potentially doubling the exposure levels (Thiery et al., 2021).

Southern Europe will face increased risk of dangerous wildfires (Costa et al., 2020). This will lead to more children being exposed to wildfire smoke (Mills et al., 2018), and is associated with increased mortality, morbidity, and hospital admissions and exacerbates respiratory and cardiovascular conditions (Liu et al., 2015). However, humidity increase in northern Europe may reduce fire frequency (Dupuy et al., 2020).

Water quality & quantity: drought, extreme precipitation, floods

Exposure

Extremely high temperatures are a well-documented consequence of climate change, which can lead to an increased prevalence of droughts (Hoerling et al., 2012). On the other hand, Europe is projected to see more days of heavy rainfall due to climate change, leading to an increased risk of flash floods in water-bound areas, which can cause health issues and fatalities (Wolf et al., 2015). 238 events of floods have been recorded between 1975 and 2005 (Hajat et al., 2005). Floods driven by recent precipitation have become more frequent over the past 70 years, while those caused by snowmelt have decreased (Jiang et al., 2022). They can degrade water quality due to sudden rises in water levels and overflow from sanitation systems and fields (Wolf et al., 2015). Coastal flooding from rising sea levels is also a concern, with various health implications, including acute physical effects and mental health consequences (Hajat et al., 2005). Given the frequency of floods and extreme precipitation, Europe faces significant disease burdens⁽⁵⁾.

Observed health effects

One million European children were living in areas with extremely high drought severity in 2015, exposed to a great risk of suffering from heat-related illnesses (UNICEF, 2015). Children are particularly vulnerable to illnesses due to physiological and behavioral factors that increase their exposure to outdoor environments, as discussed in Chapter 5.2. Elongated periods of drought can result in water shortages, which often put agricultural irrigation systems under severe strain. Inadequate irrigation of fields can lead to crop losses and failing cooling systems may increase outbreaks of food-borne diseases. Both factors can drive up the incidence of malnourished children. If water scarcity goes so far that safe drinking water becomes a rarity or if children simply get dehydrated due to the hot weather conditions and not enough self-initiative to drink water frequent enough, they may increasingly suffer from electrolyte imbalance due to insufficient fluid intake (Myers et al., 2017; Weilhhammer et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2012). Children are particularly vulnerable to health consequences of floods due to their behavioral patterns, such as spending increased time outdoors, playing and swimming in water, or engaging in hand-to-mouth activities.

⁽⁵⁾ Retrieved on 16/01/2024 from https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-your-voice/news/how-climate-change-disrupting-rainfall-patterns-and-putting-our-health-risk-2023-08-03_en

Acute diseases triggered by flooding events

During flooding events, children may use floodplains as playgrounds, contaminated or fertilized soils are washed out, sewage systems possibly overflow, leading to algae blooms and contaminated water sources, or food may not be adequately stored due to power outages. All these factors contribute to an increased incidence of water and foodborne disease infections, with children being among the high-risk age groups. Especially poor water quality at bathing water sites after prolonged heavy precipitation and runoff can become dangerous sources of infection and pose a public health problem, especially for children (Al Aukidy & Verlicchi, 2017; Crampton & Ragusa, 2023; Penna et al., 2021; Roijackers & Lürling, 2007). The most common water- and food-borne infections in children are caused by pathogens such as *Campylobacter* spp., *Salmonella* spp., *Adenovirus*, *Norovirus*, *Poliovirus*, *Coxsackievirus*, *Echovirus*, *Giardia lamblia*, and *Cryptosporidium parvum*, causing gastrointestinal symptoms like diarrhea, fever, stomach cramps, and vomiting (Collier et al., 2015; Hlavsa et al., 2014; Hokajärvi et al., 2013; Korajkic et al., 2018; Wade et al., 2008). The most important food and water-borne diseases for children's health in Europe are explained in more detail under chapter 5.5. Contaminated recreational water sources have also been associated with respiratory diseases, eye or ear infections and dermatological issues (Ashbolt, 2004; Wade et al., 2008).

Chronic diseases triggered by flooding events

Higher rates of mental disorders such as anxiety, depression, and PTSD are often observed after floods, due to similar causes as previously explained in subchapter 5.3.1 (Paterson et al., 2018). A notable increase in PTSD cases among children was shown in areas affected by floods with a meta-analysis of literature (Fernandez et al., 2015). In a study conducted 28 months after the 1997 flood in southwestern Poland, 533 students aged 11 to 21 were examined. The findings revealed that 18% of the participants met all diagnostic criteria for PTSD, and this was found to be positively associated with the level of trauma exposure during the disaster (Bokszczanin, 2007).

Projected effects

Annual precipitation is expected to decline in Southern Europe and rise in the North (Huo et al., 2021). However, projections indicate an increase in extreme precipitation events across most of Europe. Flooding and extreme precipitation are expected to increase in frequency and intensity per degree warming (Myhre et al., 2019). Furthermore, a decline in snowmelt-related water quantities and earlier spring floods can be expected (Madsen et al., 2014). Such events are expected to directly lead to more injuries, mental health challenges, and food- and water-borne diseases among young populations (Aune et al., 2022).

5.3 Air pollution and Pollen

Exposure

Ozone, generated through photochemical reactions involving different pollutants, is accelerated and increases its level by high temperatures, dry conditions, and prolonged heat waves in Southern European regions (Noyes et al., 2009). Overall, it forms a self-reinforcing loop with higher concentrations of greenhouse gases (De Sario et al., 2013). Even if **emissions of key air pollutants** have declined over recent decades, air pollution levels in Europe are still not safe⁽⁶⁾. In schools, extreme weather conditions and poor classroom ventilation result in poor indoor air quality, posing significant health threats in Europe, particularly for children (Salthammer et al., 2016; WHO, 2015). The acceleration of allergic pollen-producing plants and elevated allergenic potential due to higher ozone concentrations contribute to these health issues (Beck et al., 2013). Warm winters, linked to increasing average temperatures, result in earlier spring pollen concentrations (Emberlin et al., 2002). The prevalence of pollen-induced diseases varies geographically and temporally, with grass and ragweed species in Europe, especially from the *Poaceae* or *Ambrosia* family, being significant

⁽⁶⁾ Retrieved on 30/05/2024 from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/newsroom/news/air-pollution-levels-across-europe>

biological air pollutants (García-Mozo, 2017; Rasmussen et al., 2017). Birch trees in northern, central, and eastern Europe, as well as olive trees and cypresses in the Mediterranean, play key roles (Biedermann et al., 2019; Gaussorgues, 2009; D'Amato et al., 2007). The European pollen season spans six months, influenced by climate and vegetation interactions (Lake et al., 2017).

Observed health effects

Due to their elevated minute ventilation, underdeveloped immune systems, participation in energetic activities, extended outdoor exposure, and the ongoing maturation of their lungs in the early postneonatal period, children are recognized to exhibit heightened susceptibility to air pollution and pollen (Figure 3) (Dixon, 2002; Pinkerton & Joad, 2000; EEA, 2023). Current levels of air pollution in European cities contribute to increased mortality, emergency hospital admissions, and worsening symptoms, especially for cardiorespiratory diseases and respiratory diseases (EEA, 2023; Fiore et al., 2015; Kinney, 2018). Between 2010 and 2019, an estimated 5,839 infants under one year succumbed to causes linked to air pollution in EU countries. In 2019, out of the 472 deaths among children and young individuals under 20 years old due to air pollution in the EU, the vast majority were infants under one year old (93%). Boys had a higher likelihood (0.59 per 100,000) of dying from air pollution in 2019 compared to girls (0.49 per 100,000) (Kwon et al., 2024).

Asthma

Asthma is a chronic condition with one of the highest prevalence rates among children, especially in high-income countries. It is a top-10 chronic condition globally, particularly affecting children aged 5 to 14, accounting for 4.85% of total years lived with disabilities due to asthma-related disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) (Asher & Pearce, 2014). It has been shown that high pollen concentrations in conjunction with fluctuating climatic conditions can trigger severe and widespread asthma attacks, providing strong evidence that children and adolescents exposed to outdoor pollen are at an increased risk of asthma exacerbations. Approximately 33% of European childhood asthma cases can be attributed to air pollution (Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2023). In addition, Exposure to air pollution from traffic is a major risk factor for the development of asthma in children (Tiotiu et al., 2020). During an asthma attack, the airways become inflamed and swollen, leading to breathing difficulties (Hargreave & Nair, 2009). Exposure to high concentrations of airborne pollen can worsen this condition, causing further airflow restriction and potentially life-threatening complications for individuals with asthma (D'Amato et al., 2015). Research indicates that a significant portion of asthma sufferers also have allergic rhinitis, highlighting the link between pollen exposure and asthma (Erbas et al., 2018). Additionally, asthma can manifest as pneumonia, shortness of breath, wheezing, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (Asher & Pearce, 2014).

Hay fever: allergic rhinitis, allergic rhino-conjunctivitis

Hay fever results from exposure to airborne allergens transported via pollen. Both indoor and outdoor air pollution have been firmly established as significant environmental risk factors contributing to the prevalence of hay fever, greatly influenced by various climate change-related variables (Mimura et al., 2014). Over the past half-century, there has been a remarkable increase in the prevalence of hay fever, which is now a global concern. Young children, aged between 6 and 7 years, have experienced a substantial rise in allergic rhino-conjunctivitis symptoms, with an increase of more than 65% (Jalbert & Golebiowski, 2015). The combination of higher pollen count and longer pollen seasons as well as air pollution can cause the prevalence of different types of hay fever to increase (Silverberg et al., 2015), whereby the high susceptibility of children and adolescents should be emphasized. This condition is characterized by inflammation of the nasal passages (allergic rhinitis) and the ocular membrane (allergic rhino-conjunctivitis), leading to symptoms such as redness, swollen and watery eyes, a runny or blocked nose and frequent sneezing (Blais et al., 2018).

Figure 3: Potential mechanism by which climate change could affect pediatric allergic diseases

Source: Sheffield et al., 2011.

Other atopic diseases: atopic eczema, atopic dermatitis

Clinical manifestations of atopic eczema include neurodermatitis or atopic dermatitis, and it is one of the most prevalent chronic conditions globally. Roughly 10 to 15% of children in developed Western countries are affected, exhibiting a prevalence rate four times higher than that observed in adults (Augustin et al., 2021). Similar to other allergic conditions related to pollen exposure, atopic eczema is influenced, provoked or maintained by several environmental factors. For instance, children raised in proximity to busy roads where they are exposed to higher levels of fossil fuel emissions, face an elevated risk of developing atopic diseases (Kim et al., 2013). Furthermore, indoor and outdoor air pollutants can exacerbate the severity of atopic eczema in children by penetrating the deeper layers of the skin and compromising the epidermal barrier (Altunbulakli et al., 2018; Herbarth et al., 2006; Huss-Marp et al., 2006). Therefore, it is important to note that atopic eczema plays a distinctive role in the emergence of other allergic diseases, since such an epidermal barrier dysfunction makes the skin more susceptible to allergens and facilitates sensitization (Luschkova et al., 2021).

Cardiovascular diseases

Limited evidence exists regarding the relationship between pollen exposure and cardiovascular diseases, but studies in Canada and the United States have linked airborne allergens to increased risk of heart attacks, particularly among individuals with existing allergic symptoms. Air pollution, especially PM2.5, is consistently associated with cardiovascular risk factors, with long-term exposure potentially worsening conditions like hypertension and diabetes. These changes may increase the risk of cardiovascular events over time, particularly concerning for children and young adults facing a lifetime of higher exposures (Weichenthal et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2010; Anenberg et al., 2020; Bergmann & Sypniewska, 2011; Theoharides & Kalogeromitros, 2006).

Neurodevelopmental impairment due to chemical exposure

Mercury is one of the chemicals that significantly increased due to enhanced release from melting permafrost. Mercury has been identified as a neurotoxin by several studies and linked to impaired brain development. Cognitive, language, motor, immunological, and visual disorders have been observed in children exposed to elevated mercury concentrations. Already, pregnant women are advised against consuming predatory fish species such as tuna or swordfish because of this (Davidson et al., 2004; Bose-O'Reilly et al., 2010).

Health effects due to mold indoors

Another indoor air pollution that particularly affects children is the exposure to mold. Mold can be used as a general term for various fungi which may occur as visible mold in indoor environments (Hurrass et al., 2017). There is some evidence that climate change may increase the severity of indoor

and atmospheric mold exposure, for example when housing is left moisture after flooding (D'Amato et al., 2020). Exposure to indoor mold can have various health effects on children. The specific health effects can vary depending on the type of mold, the extent of exposure, and the individual's sensitivity. One of the first signs of mold exposure can be skin irritation, with some eczema, dry, scaly skin, and itchy skin (Seltzer & Fedoruk, 2007; Curtis et al., 2009). Many studies have shown that mold spores can irritate the respiratory system, leading to respiratory problems, with symptoms such as coughing, wheezing, sneezing and shortness of breath. Children with asthma or other respiratory conditions may be more susceptible to these effects and will exacerbate the condition. Mold exposure can also cause neurological effects in children. Indeed, the mycotoxin release as spores can cause kill or damage to neurons, impairing brain function⁽⁷⁾ (Anyanwu et al., 2003; Curtis et al., 2009).

Projected effects

Regional projections indicate a 10%-14% rise in ozone-related health issues and fatalities from 2021 to 2050 in central Europe, with some northern European countries expecting a decrease. Further ahead, between 2041 and 2060, morbidity and mortality may increase by 34% in specific regions (Orru et al., 2013). The warming climate will extend the pollen season and shift pollen-producing vegetation distribution, increasing associated disease incidence. By 2100, allergenic ragweed species are expected to spread northward and eastward, with high allergy risk areas projected to expand by 27 to 100%, including new risk areas (Rasmussen et al., 2017). Rising global temperatures lead to an increase in pollen production, consequently raising the levels of natural allergens and exacerbating the severity of asthma and other respiratory conditions (UNICEF, 2015).

5.4 Vector-borne diseases

Exposure

Children are more vulnerable to vector-borne diseases due to the above-mentioned behavioral factors in chapter 5.2, putting them at greater risk of encountering disease-transmitting vectors like mosquitoes and ticks (Bennett and Friel, 2014). Furthermore, the likelihood of children experiencing a more severe disease outcome in case of infection is higher due to the previously mentioned physiological characteristics of children and their naive immune systems (Bunyavanich et al., 2003; Bennett and Friel, 2014). Rising temperatures can expand the habitat range of disease-carrying vectors like mosquitoes and ticks, allowing them to survive in new areas into northern regions and higher elevations across Europe (Semenza and Suk, 2018), and prolonging the disease transmission season (Patz and Reisen, 2001; Bunyavanich et al., 2003). Changes in precipitation patterns, whether increased rainfall or prolonged droughts, can further enhance vector reproduction (Ogden, 2017). Over time, disease vectors may adapt to changing climate conditions, potentially becoming more efficient disease transmitters (Voyiatzaki et al., 2022).

Observed health effects

More rainfall is leading to an increase in stagnant water bodies where mosquitoes can breed (Patz & Resien, 2001). In addition, in a warmer climate, adult female mosquitoes digest blood faster and feed more frequently, so they can increase transmission intensity (Hopp and Foley, 2001). Mosquito vectors can spread pathogens such as Zika Virus, dengue virus, or chikungunya virus transmitted by *Aedes* mosquitoes (Adachi and Nielsen, 2018; Gurugama et al., 2010). If a pregnant woman contracts the Zika virus, her child may be born with microcephaly, brain disruption, ocular anomalies, and neurodevelopmental impairments (Marbàn-Castro et al., 2021). Dengue infection can cause symptoms ranging from fever and headache to severe hemorrhagic fevers and shock syndrome, potentially fatal in children (Gurugama et al., 2010). According to the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), Europe saw 74 non-travel-associated cases in 2023, highlighting the threat of local transmission. Indeed, an increasing number of autochthonous cases have been

⁽⁷⁾ Retrieved on 11/01/2024 from <https://imold.us/surprising-effects-mold-has-on-children/>

described since 2010 (Zatta et al., 2023). Chikungunya fever can be severe in children, with neurological symptoms and hemorrhagic manifestations (Gérardin et al. 2008). A literature review and meta-analysis conducted by Nyamwaya and colleagues, 2022, show that chikungunya fever severity was more prevalent in children <1 year (Nyamwaya et al., 2022). West Nile Virus is typically transmitted by *Culex* and *Aedes* mosquitoes (Hamel et al., 2024). The majority of children infected with the virus will experience only mild symptoms. While it's still possible for children to become seriously ill, such occurrences are rare. Children with compromised immune systems or pre-existing serious illnesses are at higher risk of severe illness (retrieved from *Paediatrics & Child Health*, Volume 13, Issue 5, 2008). Finally, malaria, caused by *Plasmodium* parasites transmitted by *Anopheles* mosquitoes, poses a significant threat globally, particularly to children under five (WHO, 2023). Rising imported cases in Europe, coupled with competent vectors and favorable climatic conditions, raise concerns about resurgence. Several European countries reported locally transmitted cases, indicating the potential for re-establishment (Fischer et al., 2020).

For tick vectors, the most widely distributed ticks in Europe are *Ixodes ricinus*. It transmits the Lyme disease, the most commonly transmitted tick-borne illness to humans (Kullberg et al., 2020). The highest incidence occurs in children aged 5-14 years old (Shapiro and Gerber, 2000). Tick-Borne Encephalitis (TBE) is also becoming more prevalent with the increase in temperature (Nah et al., 2019). It mainly affects school-age children (Rostasy, 2012). Sandfly vectors can spread Leishmaniasis, that is a disease caused by protozoa from the *Leishmania* genus, is primarily found in tropical and subtropical regions but can also occur elsewhere. Factors like poor living conditions and climate change contribute to the spread of leishmaniasis, attracting sandflies to new regions (Fischer et al., 2011). Children under 10 are one of the most vulnerable populations, because of their less developed immune system (Elmahallawy et al., 2021).

Projected effects

Climate change is a key driver behind the expansion of arthropod vectors and the rise of vector-borne diseases (Voyiatzaki et al., 2022). Europe will most likely experience significant increases in exposure to viruses transmitted by vectors, such as *Aedes* genus (Liu-Helmersson et al., 2019). Dengue fever poses a heightened risk in Europe due to climate-induced changes in *Aedes albopictus* population density and seasonal activity, with potential re-establishment of *A. aegypti*. Lyme disease is expected to remain a significant health concern for children, with a projected 3.8% expansion of *Ixodes ricinus* habitat in Europe by 2040-2050, extending into higher altitudes and latitudes (Boeckmann and Joyner, 2014). TBE incidence is likely to shift towards higher altitudes and latitudes, increasing risk in northern and central Europe (Semenza and Menne, 2009). Malaria transmission season lengthening is anticipated, with predictive models suggesting an extension beyond Southern Europe and the Mediterranean area, affecting Central and Eastern Europe and the North Balkan region, including prolonged transmission in Germany and the UK (Holy et al., 2011; Lindsay et al., 2018). Leishmaniasis vectors are expected to extend northward, with an increase in species capable of transmitting the disease in Central Europe (Koch et al., 2017). Warmer temperatures enable mosquitoes and ticks to thrive in broader areas, potentially exposing children to diseases previously uncommon in their regions (Bellone & Failloux, 2020).

5.5 Food- and water-borne disease pathogens

Exposure

Young children under 5 years old face the highest risk of food- and water-borne diseases in Europe (WHO, 2017; Cassini et al., 2016). Extreme weather events like floods and heavy rainfall, along with rising temperatures and increased salinity, contribute to the prevalence of these illnesses (Phung et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2019; Rahaman et al., 2020). Changes in animal distribution due to climate change can introduce zoonotic diseases into the food supply chain, further endangering children (Leibler et al., 2009). Water-borne diseases, a persistent global concern, disproportionately affect

children, especially those lacking proper sanitation and clean water access (Griffiths, 2008). Infrastructure damage from extreme weather events can lead to contaminated floodwater and outbreaks of diseases like cryptosporidiosis and giardiasis (Semenza, 2020; Semenza et al., 2022). Despite efforts to improve water quality, microbial contamination remains a significant issue, causing outbreaks that affect children in both low- and high-income countries (Dicker et al., 2022; Ferreira et al., 2021). Similarly, food-borne diseases pose a significant threat to young children, with 40% of the burden falling on those under 5 years old (WHO, 2017). Floods and heavy rainfall can contaminate crops, increasing the risk of consuming tainted food and contracting illnesses like Salmonella or Campylobacter infections (Ahmed et al., 2016). Warmer temperatures further exacerbate the growth of food-borne pathogens, leading to more outbreaks, particularly in Europe (Dietrich et al., 2023).

Observed health effects

Food- and water-borne diseases can have several impacts on children as they are more vulnerable to these diseases, especially infants and children under 5 years old. **Campylobacteriosis** is the disease with the highest burden in EU/EEA countries, and is a leading cause of bacterial gastroenteritis, with children under 5 bearing the highest disease burden. It is closely followed by **salmonellosis**, being a significant cause of foodborne outbreaks, particularly affecting infants and children under 5. With other bacterial infections, such as **E. coli**, and **Vibrio**, all the diseases have the highest number of confirmed cases reported in infants and children (Cassini et al., 2016). Some parasites can also be transmitted through food and water affecting the young generation (Cacciò & Chalmers, 2016). **Cryptosporidium** parasite can cause diarrheal disease (Dietrich et al., 2023). The disease's prevalence in children is attributed to substandard hygiene practices and limited immunity (Cacciò & Chalmers, 2016). **Giardia** infections are associated with malnutrition, cognitive impairment, and growth issues in children (Prado et al., 2005; Berkman et al., 2002). Proper hygiene and food safety practices are essential to prevent outbreaks and protect vulnerable populations. Repeated episodes of food- and water-borne diseases can lead to malnutrition. The loss of essential nutrients due to diarrhea and vomiting, combined with a reduced appetite, can result in stunted growth, where children fail to reach their expected height and weight milestones (Guerrant et al., 2009). Malnutrition resulting from food- and water-borne diseases can impair cognitive development, potentially affecting a child's ability to learn and perform well in school (Jyoti et al., 2005). Some food- and water-borne diseases can have long-term health consequences, even if the acute symptoms subside (Acheson, 2009). Diarrheal diseases caused by contaminated food or water can lead to rapid fluid loss, increasing the risk of dehydration in children (WHO, 2017).

Projected effects

Concerns rise over how altered precipitation patterns may affect water- and food-borne disease transmission; projections vary by region and climate change severity, with northern Europe expecting a 5–20% precipitation increase and southern Europe anticipating a decrease of 5–30% (Semenza et al., 2012; Ebi et al., 2018). In Europe, the average yearly count of temperature-related salmonellosis cases under high emissions scenarios could surge by up to 50% beyond what would be anticipated solely based on population growth by the year 2100 (Lake, 2017). In Denmark, all recent instances of Campylobacter outbreaks via water have occurred after abnormally heavy rainfall, indicating that anticipated climate shifts pose a significant concern regarding Campylobacter epidemiology (Kuhn et al., 2017). Rising temperatures elevate bacterial contamination risks within the food supply chain; warmer weather accelerates Salmonella reproduction and promotes Vibrio bacteria replication in marine waters, linked to illness and mortality (Lake, 2017; Semenza et al., 2017). Campylobacteriosis cases in Scandinavian countries are projected to nearly triple by the century's end (Kuhn et al., 2020). Parasites show resilience to environmental changes, hinting at their potential future prevalence as pathogens. Extreme weather events like heavy rainfall and flooding, expected to become more

frequent due to climate change, heighten the risk of infectious oocysts/cysts contaminating water bodies and plant-based foods (Dietrich et al., 2023).

5.6 Food insecurity

Exposure

Due to global warming, Europe, in particular, has seen a rise in droughts frequency (Agostoni et al., 2023), impacting crop yields and food supplies due to air pollution and soil and freshwater acidification (Poursafa and Kelishadi, 2011). Heat waves also have severe consequences, inducing heat stress in livestock, reducing productivity, and affecting overall animal health and biodiversity (Agostoni et al., 2023). These changes contribute to a decline in both the quality and quantity of food (Myers et al., 2017)⁽⁸⁾. Moreover, rising temperatures create ideal conditions for pest and disease proliferation, further impacting plant and livestock populations negatively (Agostoni et al., 2023). Food insecurity is defined through various lenses. Initially, it entails a quantitative aspect, indicating insufficient food availability within households. Then, a qualitative dimension emerges, reflecting changes in dietary patterns and supplies, characterized by limited diversity, imbalanced nutrition, and the absence of healthy foods. Moreover, a psychological dimension involves feelings of unease and worry regarding food availability. Lastly, a social dimension is evident, marked by adjustments in food-related practices, such as seeking aid from charities or resorting to theft (Loopstra, 2018; Radimer, Olson & Campbell, 1990; Food and Agricultural Organization, 2015).

Observed health effects

In recent years, several European countries have seen a rise in food insecurity rates (Loopstra et al., 2015). Notably, the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Slovakia have reported high household food insecurity rates, ranging from 10% to 22%, with an upward trend. Other countries like the United Kingdom, Hungary, Greece, and Italy have also experienced significant increases, with prevalence rising from 7% to 17% (Pettoello-Mantovani et al., 2018). In contrast, Poland and Slovenia have seen a slight decrease (>1%) in food insecurity prevalence, while Austria, Germany, and Portugal, after a decade-long decline, show rates ranging from 3% to 8%.

Weight status: underweight and obesity/overweight

Food-insecure children are at risk of both undernutrition and overnutrition. Undernutrition is the largest threat to health as a result of climate change (Agostoni et al., 2023). The consequences of reduced availability, quality, and accessibility of food from the agricultural and livestock sectors include an increased risk of nutrient deficiencies and undernutrition. This, in turn, can lead to short-term consequences like anemia as well as long-term effects, such as cognitive and physical developmental issues. Moreover, it may predispose individuals to overweight and other non-communicable diseases later in life (Victoria et al., 2021; Grey et al., 2021).

On the other hand, when food is insecure, people may consume calorie-dense but nutrient-poor foods, increasing the risk of obesity and related health issues. Indeed, when faced with food insecurity, people often resort to a 'substitution' effect, opting for more calorie-dense foods, typically high in simple carbohydrates and fat, as they are more cost-effective in terms of calories compared to higher-quality, lower-calorie-density alternatives (Seligman et al., 2010; Drewnowski, 2004). Nevertheless, even if a link has been shown in adults, it should be noted that the results concerning a link between overweight/obesity and food insecurity remain conflicted for children (Jyoti et al., 2005; Willis & Fitzpatrick, 2016).

Developmental disorders

Food insecurity often results in inadequate access to a balanced diet, and children consume fewer fruits and vegetables (Hanson & Connor, 2014). This, in turn, can result in malnutrition, which may

⁽⁸⁾ Retrieved on 30/05/2024 from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/european-climate-risk-assessment>

manifest as impaired growth or have long-lasting consequences for both physical and cognitive development. In fact, inadequate intake of essential energy, protein, and micronutrients during the initial five years of life can restrict neural plasticity and result in compromised cognitive function (Prado & Dewey, 2014; Georgieff et al., 2015). In addition, the impacts of hunger and poor nutrition extend into a child's educational sphere, affecting their ability to concentrate and actively engage in school. This, in turn, may lead to lower academic performance, with potentially long-lasting consequences for their educational journey (Winicki & Jemison, 2003; Jyoti et al., 2005). Concerning physical developmental issues, food insecurity can often lead to wasting and stunting in children (Bhutta et al., 2017).

Mental health

In line with impaired neuronal development due to malnutrition early in life, it can then result in an increased risk of mental illness, such as depression and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder among children (Adan et al., 2019). Significant correlations were seen between food insecurity and depression among children aged 2 to 17 years old (Thomas et al., 2019), potentially impacting their emotions, such as feeling low, irritable, or nervous (Molcho et al., 2007).

Projected effects

Climate change exerts a direct impact on crop production, with estimated declines of 3.1-7.4% in global yields of essential crops for each one-degree Celsius increase in the global mean temperature (Zhao et al., 2017). According to recent projections that use 2014 as a reference, a substantial increase in production, ranging from 25% to 70%, will be imperative to meet the escalating demand for crops by 2050 (Hunter et al., 2017). Additionally, altered precipitation patterns and prolonged droughts can result in water scarcity, affecting agricultural irrigation (Myers et al., 2017). This, in turn, may lead to diminished crop yields and restricted food production. Consequently, this can trigger food shortages and price spikes, ultimately exacerbating food insecurity. In fact, one model suggests that inflation-adjusted prices for the world's three most vital staple grains—wheat, rice, and maize—could surge by 31–106% by 2050 (Nelson et al., 2010). Furthermore, food quality will also be affected by climate change. The elevated level of carbon dioxide and the increased temperature would impact yields and micronutrients composition of rice, wheat, legumes, nuts, vegetables, and fruits. Most of the studies showed that elevated temperature reduced the yield and zinc, iron and vitamin A micronutrients (Semba et al., 2022). It will also affect crop yields, leading to nutritional deficiencies and growth stunting in children, and escalating the risk of undernutrition, which is particularly damaging during the early stages of a child's development (Amondo et al., 2023).

6 Responses in policy and practice

6.1 Taxonomy of interventions

The intervention implemented to counter children's health risk due to climate change will be classified following the taxonomy suggested by Leitner & colleagues, 2021. The five categories are:

Physical and Technological approaches concentrate on tangible solutions for challenges or goals, including infrastructure and technology. This includes **grey options**, which are traditional or conventional approaches involving the construction of physical infrastructure or the use of established technologies, as well as **technological options** that utilize innovative or advanced technologies to develop new solutions or enhance existing ones in addressing challenges and achieving goals.

The **Nature-based Solutions and Ecosystem-based Approaches** category highlights the utilization of natural systems and processes to address challenges or achieve goals, recognizing the significance of ecosystems in providing services and benefits to society. It encompasses **green options**, which are nature-based solutions utilizing vegetation, such as forests, wetlands, or green spaces, to address challenges or achieve goals, often focusing on benefits like carbon sequestration, flood mitigation, biodiversity conservation, or shading spaces. Additionally, **blue options** involve utilizing aquatic or marine ecosystems, such as rivers, lakes, or coastal areas, to address challenges or achieve goals, often focusing on benefits like water purification, coastal protection, or fisheries management.

Most of the interventions that respond to the health risks of climate change and are specifically targeted to children can be classified under the **Knowledge and Behavioral Change** category. It underscores the importance of education, awareness, and behavioral change in addressing challenges and achieving goals, recognizing the pivotal role of human attitudes and actions. It includes **information and awareness-raising**, which involves disseminating information and employing communication strategies to increase understanding and awareness of specific issues or solutions among individuals or communities. Moreover, **capacity building, empowering, and lifestyle practices** focus on enhancing the knowledge, skills, and capabilities of individuals or communities to enable them to take informed action, as well as promoting lifestyle changes or behaviors contributing to desired goals or outcomes. Interventions targeting education, preparedness, and awareness are pivotal (Seddighi et al., 2020). These efforts, implemented in settings like schools, kindergartens, and child welfare centers, play a crucial role in disaster risk reduction. Schools serve as key platforms for educating children, while tools like serious games and mobile apps aid in preparedness and reducing exposure to disasters. Post-disaster interventions also mitigate potential health effects (Lazarus et al., 2003).

Governance and institutions are crucial for effective decision-making and implementation in societies or organizations. This includes **policy** formulation to address issues or achieve goals, **management and planning** for resource coordination, and coordination, cooperation, and networks for collaboration among stakeholders to tackle shared challenges or objectives.

The **Economic and Finance** category delves into the financial aspects crucial for addressing challenges, or achieving goals, particularly in terms of funding and risk management. It consists of **financing and incentive instruments**, which encompass various financial mechanisms and incentives used to mobilize funds and resources for specific purposes or projects. Moreover, **insurance and risk-sharing instruments** are employed to mitigate financial risks associated with certain activities or events.

In this report, only the four first categories will be elaborated in this report, as no intervention in the category "Economic and Finance" has been found.

6.2 Overview of intervention application in Europe

This chapter will be structured by climate exposure and following the taxonomy of the four categories of interventions just mentioned.

Table 2: Summary of interventions by type of measures

	Extreme weather events	Air pollution & Pollen	Vector-borne diseases	Food- and water-borne diseases	Food insecurity
Nature-based Solutions and Ecosystem-based Approach	Coolschools: OASIS Besançon: School playground	Planting Healthy Air in Schools program			
Physical and Technological	myBUILDINGisGREEN LIFE RESILIO	SINPHONIE BREATHE			
Knowledge and Behavioral Change	EXTREMA Extreme heat in UK schools AdSWiM WATERCARE Hull Children’s Flood	NAAF Astma- en Allergiekoepel BreatheLife	Toolkits for schools Online educational video games	Toolkits for schools	
Governance and institutions (policy)	Recommendation on learning for the green transition and sustainable development Heat-Health action plan		TBE vaccine recommendations and reimbursements		

Extreme weather events

In addressing the diverse challenges of climate change, interventions are crucial across various domains. The different strategies aim to mitigate the impact of extreme weather events, encompassing heat waves, wildfires, flooding, water quality and quantity, and storms, on the well-being of children.

Nature-based Solutions and Ecosystem-based Approaches/ Physical and Technological

In cities, the heat waves are amplified by the phenomenon of UHI) caused by the density of buildings, the mineral and impervious characteristics of infrastructure materials, which multiplies their consequences. Climate change will lead to more frequent heavy rainfall and flooding. Consequently, it is important to enhance water infiltration, storage, and absorption, which will also aid in mitigating heat through evapotranspiration. Addressing these challenges requires involving citizens of all ages in the design and management of their immediate urban surroundings. Urban planning initiatives prioritize green spaces and resilient infrastructure, as well as distributing heat-resistant materials to counteract heat-related risks (Baró et al., 2022). Governments increasingly adopt nature-based solutions for flood management, including widening floodplains and investing in green spaces (Jongman, 2018).

- Coolschools: OASIS (2018-2021)

It is in this context that the COOLSCHOOLS project started. The project takes place in four main cities: Brussels, Barcelona, Rotterdam, and Paris. The OASIS project in Paris, which started in 2018, aims to address climate and social challenges by transforming 10 schoolyards into cool islands using innovative techniques and nature-based solutions. Now, more than 130 schools in Paris have an OASIS schoolyard⁽⁹⁾. It aims to reduce health risks from heat waves and enhance social cohesion at the neighborhood level. By creating cool islands and reducing the urban heat island effect, OASIS lowers temperatures and improves summer comfort in schoolyards while also improving rainwater management and developing green and blue infrastructures. The project introduced new governance and participatory management practices for local public facilities and promoted awareness and education about climate change adaptation through participatory approaches. By involving children, civil servants, residents, and educational communities, OASIS seeks to build knowledge and collective commitment to addressing climate challenges. Ultimately, the project aims to strengthen social bonds by providing accessible spaces, developing new activities, and implementing inclusive democratic protocols, as evidenced by the varied use of schoolyards during school and extracurricular hours⁽¹⁰⁾.

- Besançon: School playground (2020-2022)

The initiative reimagines playgrounds to prioritize children's needs over traditional asphalt yards dominated by ball games. At Pierre-Brossolette school, a 5,000-m² playground has been transformed into a permeable, green space with trees, grassy areas, and nature corners. This inclusive design encourages equal participation, reconnects children with nature, and supports diverse activities like gardening.

The project aims to renovate four to five playgrounds annually, funded by the city, water agency, and region. Initial observations highlight collaboration among city departments and community involvement, with children participating in tree planting. The new playground opened in September 2021, and while it is too early for definitive conclusions, initial feedback suggests challenges in balancing sports and general physical activity and maintaining the space. Despite some resistance

⁽⁹⁾ Retrieved on 13/02/2024 from <https://www.uia-initiative.eu/en/pdf/3058>

⁽¹⁰⁾ Retrieved on 14/02/2024 from <https://www.uia-initiative.eu/fr/uia-cities/paris-call3> and <https://coolschools.eu/>

from children who miss traditional sports facilities, the new playground design is viewed as essential for making schools community hubs⁽¹¹⁾.

- RESILIO (2018-2021)

A modern approach to counteract the negative health implications due to extreme heat has been developed in the framework of the RESILIO (Resilience nEtwork of Smart Innovative cLimate-adaptive roOoftops) project. It was implemented in 2018-2022 by the city of Amsterdam and co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund through the Urban Innovative Actions Initiative. Amsterdam is facing climate change effects like flash floods, higher temperatures, and increased droughts. The RESILIO project seeks to tackle urban climate challenges by repurposing rooftops in vulnerable neighborhoods. With 10,000m² of smart blue-green roofs, the project aims to mitigate heavy rain impacts, reducing flood risks, urban heat island effect, and drought while enhancing building insulation, biodiversity, and quality of life, aiding the city's adaptation efforts. Another advantage of the roofs are that they can also be used as exercise space, including safe playgrounds for children⁽¹²⁾. Evidence supports that having access to green spaces is beneficial for health and well-being across all age groups. In the case of children, such access yields advantages concerning physical health, mental well-being, and behavioral development. Enhancing this environmental aspect in all nations can serve to foster and enhance the well-being of children (Kwon et al., 2024).

The originally-hypothesized temperature buffering offered by the roofs was demonstrated by the experimental work of Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS), suggesting the RESILIO roofs can contribute to insulation – and by extension energy consumption savings. Alternative designs for sedum, herbaceous and roof-garden roof typologies were assessed in terms of biodiversity enhancement. Moreover, the project demonstrated where real opportunities lie for future RESILIO roof development: this was demonstrated using GIS-based and hydrological model analysis to find the most suitable areas and buildings for upscaling⁽¹³⁾. Besides blue green roofs offering safe playgrounds for children, workshops were created to engage children in the topic. For example, children could paint their own vision and interpretation of a green city on a large canvas in local bookstores, creating a pathway for open communication with residents.

- myBUILDINGisGREEN LIFE (2019-2021)

Solana de los Barros, a municipality in Badajoz province, Extremadura, Spain, faces significant climate challenges. Temperatures are expected to rise by 4°C by the century's end, with fewer cold days and more heat waves. Annual rainfall is projected to decrease by 20%. School buildings need renovation to adapt to these changes, focusing on insulation for comfort and health.

The myBUILDINGisGREEN LIFE project, spanning from 2019 to 2021, implemented and tested several Nature-based Solutions (NbS) at a primary school in Solana de los Barros. These NbS, falling into four categories (green roofs, green facades, ventilation systems, and outdoor area development), aimed to enhance the school's resilience to climate change impacts such as heat and water scarcity. Green roofs, with features like inner air chambers and sustainable substrates, reduced temperatures and promoted local biodiversity. The green facades system utilized planters and climbing plants to regulate humidity and temperatures, while a ventilation system promoted natural air circulation to improve indoor air quality. Outdoor interventions included tree planting and porous paving. A comprehensive

(11) Retrieved on 27/05/2024 from https://www.santepubliquefrance.fr/content/download/582048/document_file/578078_spf00004339.pdf?version=1

(12) Retrieved on 28/11/2023 from <https://uia-initiative.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/A%20roof%20journey%20-%20RESILIO%20final%20report.pdf>

(13) Retrieved on 28/11/2023 from <https://www.uia-initiative.eu/en/news/journal-3-completing-and-delivering-resilio-smart-bluegreen-roofs-1>

monitoring plan was developed to assess the impact of these interventions on various factors, continuing until spring 2028 to evaluate their long-term effects.

The success of adaptation actions at the renovated school building in Solana de los Barros was bolstered by collaborative efforts among project partners and the school community. This collaboration facilitated tailored solutions addressing the actual needs of students and staff, while also providing valuable data for monitoring adaptation outcomes. The diverse composition of project partners, bringing together various skills and expertise, was crucial for designing and monitoring the selected measures. Encouraging results from the monitoring program further contributed to the success, paving the way for replication in other schools and buildings. Various local, regional, and national authorities were engaged to explore the transferability potential of the solutions. These institutions provided advice on key aspects such as incorporating NbS in construction regulations and promoting their use through incentives. Declarations of interest were signed with multiple municipalities in the province of Badajoz to promote NbS for climate adaptation in public buildings, with support from the Spanish Ministry of Transport, Mobility, and Urban Agenda. The renovated school building has emerged as a regional reference for sustainable construction, garnering significant interest in its maintenance from the Badajoz Provincial Council and the Solana de los Barros municipality. However, some barriers were encountered, including limited local availability of construction companies with specialized skills and inaccurate scheduling of maintenance services. Conflictual issues among contractors and challenges with selected plant species also posed obstacles, along with high costs of certain NbS. These barriers necessitated the exploration of alternative solutions to proceed with the project implementation⁽¹⁴⁾.

Knowledge and Behavioral Change

Educational programs play a pivotal role in raising awareness about health risks associated with extreme weather events such as heat waves, floods, and wildfires among children (Casartelli & Mysiak, 2023). During and after such natural disasters, parents and teachers or school employees become crucial support for children, by engaging discussions at home or within the classroom, providing psychological support, and adapting to the situation (Lazarus et al., 2003)⁽¹⁵⁾. Change in habits is also important to ensure a good environment for learning in schools, and comfort in everyday life.

- EXTREMA

This project is a mobile application called Extreme Temperature Alerts for Europe (EXTREMA). The whole population, from children to the elderly, can use this mobile application to provide personalized information regarding heat-health risks. The application delivers valuable insights by considering user profiles, including factors such as age and chronic diseases associated with higher heat wave risks, as well as specific medication usage. Users can access information such as the nearest cooling centers, their opening hours, and other pertinent details. Currently operational in Athens, Greece; Mallorca, Spain; Milan, Italy; Paris, France; and Rotterdam, Netherlands, the EXTREMA application represents a proactive measure to enhance public awareness and preparedness (WHO, 2021; National Observatory of Athens, 2020). In 2018, EXTREMA made its debut at the Climate School Berlin-Athens event: "Open Societies and Schools in Climate Protection and Energy Transition." This project aimed to raise awareness about climate change and energy consumption within the school communities of the

⁽¹⁴⁾ Retrieved on 05/12/2023 from https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/case-studies/nature-based-solutions-in-schools-a-green-way-to-adapt-buildings-to-climate-change-in-solana-de-los-barros-extremadura-spain/#challenges_anchor and <https://life-mybuildingisgreen.eu/en/home/>

⁽¹⁵⁾ Retrieved on 11/01/2024 from <https://www.nasponline.org/resources-and-publications/resources-and-podcasts/school-safety-and-crisis/natural-disaster-resources/helping-children-after-a-wildfire-tips-for-caregivers-and-teachers>

Municipality of Athens. The response to EXTREMA was notable, with over 300 students and teachers engaging with the EXTREMA services and downloading the EXTREMA Athens mobile app⁽¹⁶⁾.

- Extreme heat in UK schools

In schools, classroom temperatures are very important, not just for the health and safety of children and teachers, but also for teaching and learning. As an example, in the UK, they specifically mentioned that if the temperatures exceed sensible limits, then the employer should undertake a risk assessment and put in place measures to tackle the issue, which could include the use of blinds, fans or additional cooling, such as ventilation. In addition, when appropriate, schools can also order partial or total closure of the building⁽¹⁷⁾. Uniform rules should also be less strict, children should instead wear loose, light-colored clothes⁽¹⁸⁾.

- The AdSWiM (2019-2022) and WATERCARE (2019-2021)

Both the AdSWiM and WATERCARE projects, spanning Italy and Croatia, started communication strategies with the primary goal of cultivating environmental awareness among young individuals and educators. These strategies employed a variety of channels, including online seminars, access to open databases, and direct engagement with subject matter experts, all aimed at enlightening students about the intricate ecological issues surrounding water contamination.

Across eight cities in both Italy and Croatia, AdSWiM orchestrated various communication activities, facilitating direct engagement with students. An initiative emerged in 2020 with the creation of a didactic module based on the "take action" concept. This module, targeted at both teachers and primary school pupils, emphasized the promotion of seawater and coastline protection, alongside education about wastewater management. AdSWiM's local events were marked by the establishment of didactic laboratories, engaging diverse populations such as students, families (particularly those with children), and the general public. These laboratories served as platforms for immersive educational experiences centered on the processes of wastewater treatment plants and the water cycle. Furthermore, AdSWiM developed a specialized lab and workshop kit tailored for children, fostering interactive learning experiences. Similarly, WATERCARE's communication strategy was designed to engage a diverse array of target groups, including students. The aim was to bolster awareness regarding the project's objectives and, more importantly, to motivate individuals to take proactive steps towards environmental stewardship. WATERCARE's approach involved delivering presentations to students from Italian and Croatian students, through seminars and conferences.

AdSWiM's impact was profound, as evidenced by approximately 135 articles published across local, regional, and national media outlets, reaching nearly 7 million readers. Additionally, the project hosted or participated in a staggering 110 events, spanning in-person, online, and blended formats. Notably, AdSWiM's didactic module engaged multiple partners from Italy and Croatia, involving 51 teachers and nearly 600 primary school pupils. A total of twelve hands-on laboratories for children were conducted across various venues, including museums, local schools, and summer camps. The WATERCARE project organized six public events, with a primary focus on targeting students. Despite restrictions necessitating a shift to online platforms, the mission is to raise awareness among students about microbial pollution in bathing waters and environmental quality. Notably, the "Art & Science" component of WATERCARE proved immensely successful, leveraging creative expressions such as

⁽¹⁶⁾ Retrieved 07/11/2023 from <https://extrema.space/>

⁽¹⁷⁾ Retrieved on 05/02/2024 from <https://www.nasuwt.org.uk/static/b1e20158-e2d9-456c-8b7e4b8d40668bf3/Excessive-Temperatures-Bulletin-June-2022.pdf>

⁽¹⁸⁾ Retrieved on 05/02/2024 from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/hot-weather-and-health-supporting-vulnerable-people/looking-after-children-and-those-in-early-years-settings-during-heatwaves-for-teachers-and-professionals>

drawings, video productions, and theatrical performances to effectively convey ecological themes and foster heightened understanding and awareness among students.

Both projects not only demonstrated a commitment to environmental education but also showcased innovative approaches to engaging and empowering young individuals as active participants in environmental conservation efforts (Baldrighi et al., 2022).

- Hull Children's Flood Project (2007-2011)

This project delves into the aftermath of the summer 2007 floods in Kingston-upon-Hull, UK, a crisis that impacted over 8,600 households and 91 schools. Through a participatory research approach, the report examines the experiences of children and young people in dealing with flood resilience and recovery. While the initial flood event may have sparked excitement among children, the ensuing long-term recovery process proved to be stressful. The research, funded by various organizations, engaged children aged 9-19 through storyboards, interviews, and focus groups, with objectives including documenting their experiences and evaluating the role of support systems in their resilience.

Findings revealed the diverse experiences of children during floods, highlighting the absence of a singular 'child's perspective.' Shared experiences underscored potential avenues for improving disaster recovery efforts. These included disruptions to routines and social relations, particularly challenging for children affected both at school and home, compounded by the city's socio-economic context characterized by deprivation. Moreover, the initial excitement of the flood event quickly gave way to stress, emphasizing the importance of prioritizing the recovery process. Children articulated the upheaval and losses experienced, with coping strategies influenced by the reactions of parents and teachers. Active involvement in the recovery process, such as participation in family discussions and practical assistance, positively impacted children's ability to cope. The research highlights gaps in support for older children and adolescents transitioning between schools' post-disaster. Recommendations include prioritizing understanding and supporting children during recovery, actively involving them in the process, considering long-term implications on education, and adopting a flexible approach to supporting vulnerable children. Frontline workers interacting with children need support, and children's voices should be integrated into resilience-building initiatives, particularly related to climate change. Storyboards can help incorporate children's perspectives into policy and practice. Additionally, more resources should be allocated for rapid research commissioning after disasters (Walker et al., 2010).

Governance and institutions

In June 2022, the Council of the European Union (EU) adopted a Recommendation on learning for the green transition and sustainable development. This policy statement emphasizes the integration of sustainability into all levels of education and training. It urges Member States to prioritize learning for the green transition and sustainable development in their policies and programs, providing opportunities for formal and non-formal education to address the climate crisis and sustainability. The recommendation encourages the allocation of national and EU funds for investing in green and sustainable resources and infrastructure, as well as supporting educators in teaching about these issues. It emphasizes creating supportive learning environments that facilitate hands-on, interdisciplinary, and locally relevant teaching and learning. Additionally, the recommendation calls for the active involvement of students, staff, local authorities, youth organizations, and the research and innovation community in promoting sustainability education. This recommendation is accompanied by a Staff Working Document, which offers further details, evidence, and examples of good practices from across Europe⁽¹⁹⁾.

⁽¹⁹⁾ Retrieved on 01/02/2024 from <https://education.ec.europa.eu/focus-topics/green-education/learning-for-the-green-transition>

The WHO/Europe recommends countries, regions and cities in the Region to develop and implement heat–health action plans (HHAP), to prevent, respond to and contain heat-related risks to health (WHO/ Europe, 2021).

Pollen and air pollution

Due to the rising prevalence of allergic reactions and respiratory issues among children due to heightened air pollution and pollen levels, various targeted interventions have been implemented to reduce exposure. Children, due to their higher air intake relative to body weight, are particularly vulnerable to indoor air quality issues, which can significantly impact their health. Poor building construction, maintenance, cleaning, and ventilation contribute to indoor air quality problems in schools, affecting respiratory health, attendance, and learning performance⁽²⁰⁾. Public health campaigns also play a crucial role in raising awareness among parents, caregivers, and schools about effective strategies to minimize pollen and allergen exposure⁽²¹⁾.

Nature-based Solutions and Ecosystem-based Approaches

- Planting Healthy Air in Schools program

The Planting Healthy Air in Schools program, conducted in collaboration with Mapping for Change and Lancaster University, UK, focuses on transforming school grounds in London to combat air pollution. Through engaging the school community, the program raises awareness about the issue and educates on how trees and vegetation can mitigate exposure. By designing and planting green infrastructure like trees, ivy screens, and hedgerows, they aim to reduce pollution sources and monitor improvements in air quality around playgrounds. Trees and vegetation not only enhance well-being, biodiversity, and air cooling but also absorb harmful pollutants. Additionally, the program provides shade and new learning spaces for students, ultimately reducing their exposure to air pollution and safeguarding their health⁽²²⁾.

Physical and Technological

Solutions involve implementing measures such as air filtration and ventilation systems to mitigate the effects of pollen and air pollution and monitor air quality.

- SINPHONIE (2010-2012)

Despite the importance of indoor air quality in schools, research on its impacts and remedial measures has been limited compared to other building types. The SINPHONIE project, conducted from 2010 to 2012, aimed to address this gap by standardizing indoor air pollution assessment methodologies and producing recommendations for a healthier indoor environment in schools across Europe. The project involved assessing exposure levels, health effects, and remedial measures, ultimately aiming to disseminate its findings to relevant stakeholders. It is funded by the European Parliament and executed in collaboration with the European Commission. With 38 partners from 25 countries, the project sought to establish an observatory network, providing guidelines and recommendations to improve air quality in Europe⁽²³⁾.

The SINPHONIE project aimed to monitor the school environment and children's health across 23 European countries. It successfully collected data on indoor air quality and health, contributing to

⁽²⁰⁾ Retrieved on 14/12/2023 from <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC91160/lbna26738enn.pdf>

⁽²¹⁾ Retrieved on 14/12/2023 from <https://www.efanet.org/images/documents/EFABookonRespiratoryAllergiesFINAL.pdf>

⁽²²⁾ Retrieved from 14/12/2023 from <https://www.treesforcities.org/stories/planting-healthy-air-for-city-kids>

⁽²³⁾ Retrieved on 13/02/2023 from <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC91160/lbna26738enn.pdf>

policy development and environmental health actions for children. The project provided standardized methodologies, tools, and guidelines for healthy school environments in Europe, promoting capacity building in Eastern and Southern European countries. SINPHONIE's findings underscore the significance of indoor air quality in schools, revealing its impact on children's health, attendance, and performance. The project generated new exposure data and identified common indoor air pollutants, highlighting the need for improved ventilation and pollution control measures in school buildings. Addressing indoor air quality in schools requires considering outdoor air pollution, building characteristics, and operational practices. Recommendations include prioritizing indoor air quality in school location decisions, incorporating indoor air quality strategies in construction, and raising awareness through campaigns and training.

- BREATHE (2011-2016)

The project BRAin dEvelopment and Air polluTion ultrafine particles in sChool children (BREATHE) to determine if air pollution (especially the road traffic-related pollution) has any detrimental effect in neurodevelopment of schoolchildren. With this aim, air quality was assessed in indoor (classroom) and outdoor (playground) environments in 39 schools of Barcelona and Sant Cugat del Vallès in Spain. High concentrations of fine particulate matter (PM2.5), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), Black Carbon (BC, mainly emitted by incomplete combustion and especially related to diesel vehicles) ultrafine particle number concentration (UFP) and trace metals related to road traffic emissions were found. PM2.5 concentration was 1.7 times higher than the urban background levels, owing to high contributions from school activities. For instance, in the classrooms PM2.5 levels were importantly influenced by an indoor source characterised by organic carbon⁽²⁴⁾.

The findings from the BREATHE project underscore the significance of school air quality in promoting healthy brain development among children. Exposure to traffic-related air pollutants (TRAPs), particularly diesel pollutants like elemental carbon (EC) and ultrafine particles (UFP), is associated with slower cognitive development and increased behavioral problems in schoolchildren. These effects persist even after adjusting for noise levels. Additionally, neuroimaging studies reveal that TRAPs exposure is linked to altered brain network function and structural changes in key brain regions. Conversely, green spaces within school boundaries are associated with improved cognitive function and brain maturation. Commuting to school by foot, however, exposes children to PM2.5 and black carbon (BC), which can impair cognitive development. Given these findings, there is a pressing need for measures to reduce TRAPs concentrations in schools to safeguard children's brain development. Based on this study the recommendations are to raise awareness within and outside the school community about the detrimental impacts of air pollution on children's and public health. Spreading awareness can help advocate for measures aimed at reducing the use of private cars, thus minimizing traffic-related air pollution., encouraging active travel or the use of public transport for commuting to school. Implementing practices such as cleaning the classrooms after school hours, including opening windows for ventilation, and opting for environmentally friendly cleaning products can help maintain indoor air quality. Additionally, efforts to decrease traffic congestion in school surroundings and increase green spaces can mitigate pollution levels and enhance overall environmental quality. Periodically cleaning and replacing sand in playgrounds can also prevent the accumulation of pollutants. Finally, relocating schools or classrooms away from busy traffic areas can provide a long-term solution to minimize exposure to harmful pollutants (Rivas et al., 2018; Sunyer et a., 2015).

⁽²⁴⁾ Retrieved on 28/11/2023 from <https://www.uab.cat/web?cid=1096481466574&pagename=UABDivulga%2FPage%2FTemplatePageDetailArticleInvestigar¶m1=1345683978776>

Knowledge and Behavioral Change

Interventions to prevent, and increase awareness are being implemented throughout Europe.

There is a number of associations that have events at schools to increase awareness about asthma and allergic reactions due to allergens, such as pollen, and how to avoid such allergens and improve indoor air quality⁽²⁵⁾.

- NAAF

NAAF is a national advocacy and support organization for individuals grappling with asthma and allergies. The association holds ownership of the Norwegian Health Centre in Gran Canaria, Spain, and the Geilomo children's hospital in Norway. NAAF is dedicated to disseminating information regarding the diagnosis, treatment, patient education, and prevention of asthma and allergic diseases. Additionally, it actively addresses the challenges posed by the escalating diesel traffic's impact on local air quality, striving to enhance indoor environments in schools and public buildings. The organization conducts four distinct national tours, targeting selected schools and cities, with the aim of augmenting students' and teachers' knowledge about asthma, raising public awareness of asthma and COPD, and fostering understanding of respiratory health and pollen allergies among students. NAAF also organizes educational seminars on asthma, indoor and outdoor air quality for health personnel, teachers, industries, and local and national authorities⁽²⁶⁾.

- Astma- en Allergiekoepel

Astma- en Allergiekoepel is a Belgian association. They explain that if children with asthma and allergy receive adequate understanding from teachers who understand the disease and are open to the measures that come with effective management then they have fewer symptoms and perform better in school. Teachers should be able to help children living a normal life as it is what they want. But regularly children face misunderstanding. If children do something to reduce their discomfort, they are told they are exaggerating or trying to attract attention. This is usually not the case. To help teachers explain asthma and allergy in the classroom, they developed a poster for each different age group⁽²⁷⁾

- BreatheLife

It is a global initiative, urges cities and individuals worldwide to combat air pollution for the well-being of both people and the planet. Spearheaded by the World Health Organization (WHO), the UN Environment Programme (UNEP), and the Climate & Clean Air Coalition (CCAC), the campaign boasts active participation from several European nations, including Norway, Italy, Ireland, France, Belgium, Spain, and the United Kingdom. The primary goal of BreatheLife is to rally governments at the city, regional, and national levels to pledge their commitment to achieving the WHO Air Quality Guidelines by 2030. Meeting these guidelines is crucial, as it is anticipated to cut air pollution-related deaths in half by 2030 and concurrently contribute to mitigating the pace of climate change⁽²⁸⁾. To reach this goal, several campaigns are set up. One example is the SafeStreetSaveLives project, in 2020, that encourages parents and children to go to school by bicycles to reduce air pollution caused by vehicles.

⁽²⁵⁾ Retrieved on 14/12/2023 from <https://www.efanet.org/images/documents/EFABookonRespiratoryAllergiesFINAL.pdf>

⁽²⁶⁾ Retrieved on 14/12/2023 from <https://gaapp.org/diseases/asthma/>

⁽²⁷⁾ Retrieved on 14/12/2023 from <https://www.astma-en-allergiekoepel.be/astma-en-allergie-op-school/posters-met-lesverloop>

⁽²⁸⁾ Retrieved on 14/12/2023 from <https://www.ccacoalition.org/projects/breathelife-campaign>

Vector-borne diseases control

The proliferation of vectors transmitting diseases has instigated focused interventions within the domain of public health. Educational programs in schools designed to enhance awareness about the risks associated with vector-borne diseases. Such educational programs emphasize preventive measures, thereby empowering children to take proactive steps to protect themselves from catching an infection (Wilson et al., 2020). Educational programs using the involvement of the media and community health workers and leaders can strengthen public awareness. It is potentially the most important tool for transforming society in a way that can cope with climate change and its consequences (Moshou & Drinia, 2023).

Knowledge and Behavioral Change

- Toolkits at school

Some **toolkits** have been developed by the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control for EU Member States, in 2015, targeting children. As an example, one targets tick-borne disease. The goal is to raise awareness about ticks in a straightforward and easily comprehensible way, outlining what ticks are, how to prevent encounters with them, and what steps to take if children are bitten. These materials are designed for communication with children aged 7-12. Since children often seek additional guidance, it's crucial to supply supplementary resources to teachers, other professionals, and ideally, parents. This ensures they are equipped to engage in discussions with children about ticks⁽²⁹⁾.

- Educational videos games

Targeting ticks-borne diseases, with a focus on Lyme disease, an online educational video game has been created in the Netherlands. In this game, players navigate their own neighborhoods (selected via their postal code) and encounter various simulated scenarios involving the risk of tick bites. Upon completing the game, children receive their overall score and can share their results with their parents via an automatically generated email. This email also provides information to parents about ticks and Lyme Borreliosis (Beaujean et al., 2016).

Governance and institutions

- TBE vaccine recommendations and reimbursements

From the data provided to the ECDC in 2014 and 2015, out of 3953 reported cases, there were 5 cases in infants under 1 year, 5 cases in 1-year-olds, 10 cases in 2-year-olds, and between 16 and 28 cases in each individual age group of children aged 3 to 10 years. The total of 81 cases in children under 6 years old accounts for 2.0% of all reported cases. Vaccination is the most effective defense against TBE, with high seroconversion rates shown by available vaccines. However, TBE vaccine recommendations vary widely across Europe. Austria and Switzerland are the only countries with national universal vaccination programs, while other European nations base their recommendations on factors like risk areas or occupational exposure. Countries like Germany, Czech Republic, Slovenia, and Sweden recommend vaccination for those living, working, or traveling to TBE-endemic regions. In Poland, vaccine is recommended only for persons with high risk of exposure (e.g., children and adolescents in youth camps) (Kunze et al., 2022; Steffen, 2019).

⁽²⁹⁾ Retrieved on 15/12/2023 from <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/communication-toolkit-tick-borne-diseases-and-preventive-measures>

Food- and water-borne diseases

In response to the increased prevalence of food- and water-borne diseases, surveillance systems are implemented to control the proliferation. In schools, educational programs are also a key component, by using toolkits specifically designed for children⁽³⁰⁾.

Knowledge and Behavioral Change

The European Centre for Disease prevention and Control (ECDC) created a communication toolkit in 2013 to support infection prevention in schools, with a focus on gastrointestinal diseases. As described in chapter 5.6, gastrointestinal diseases are often the results of bacterial infection through food or water ingestion. In this document, they present several slogans, powerpoint presentations, pictograms (wash your hands, dry them), and posters to prevent gastrointestinal diseases⁽³¹⁾.

Food insecurity

Interventions in this domain remain rare, as Europe, at the level of households, does rarely experience food insecurity because of climate change. Interventions aiming at helping people that suffer from food insecurity because of the economic crisis are more present (Carrillo-Alvarez, 2023). In this case interventions are mostly food aid organizations as the primary response in most countries or identifying food-system issues such as food redistribution or trade dependency. Food and basic material assistance are also available for the most disadvantaged individuals and households (Carrillo-Alvarez, 2023). Interventions to counter the negative effects of climate change are more focused on agriculture with initiative to increase irrigation to combat drought and using new scientific knowledge to respond to the increased food demand⁽³²⁾.

⁽³⁰⁾ Retrieved on 19/12/2023 from https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/media/en/healthtopics/food_and_waterborne_disease/communication_toolkit/Documents/131119-gastro-toolkit-implementation-hanbook.pdf

⁽³¹⁾ Retrieved on 19/12/2023 from https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/media/en/healthtopics/food_and_waterborne_disease/communication_toolkit/Documents/131119-gastro-toolkit-implementation-hanbook.pdf

⁽³²⁾ Retrieved on 17/01/2023 from <https://www.european-views.com/2023/06/climate-crisis-forcing-europe-to-reconsider-food-security/> and <https://info.bml.gv.at/en/topics/food/food-security-in-europe-through-climate-change-research.html>

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Annex I: Scientific summary

Health issues

Climate change has a high potential to negatively affect the health of children and adolescents. They are particularly vulnerable to the adverse health impacts of climate change due to various factors. Physiologically, their developing bodies have higher surface area-to-mass ratios, making them more sensitive to environmental temperature changes (Vanos et al., 2017). Their metabolism, cardiac output, and heat dissipation mechanisms differ from adults, affecting their ability to adapt to climate shifts (Bunyavanich et al., 2003). Additionally, children have higher water intake, breathe more rapidly, and are more prone to injuries and heat-related diseases during natural disasters (D'Anci et al., 2006; Salvi et al., 2007). Their immature immune systems render children more susceptible to infections (Bunyavanich et al., 2003). Their active lifestyle, increased outdoor exposure, and breathing frequency heighten vulnerability to heat and air pollution. Hand-to-mouth activities increase the risk of exposure to environmental contaminants, and limited coping mechanisms exacerbate susceptibility during extreme weather events (Xu et al., 2014; (Ngure et al., 2019)). Children's dependency on adults for care and decision-making can hinder their ability to cope with climate-related events (Atazadeh et al., 2022). Moreover, climate-related events can have profound psychosocial effects on children, including displacement, trauma, disruptions in education, and mental health issues (Dyregrov et al., 2018; Ortega Pacheco & Barrero Toncel, 2022). In general, climate change plays a multiplier role, amplifying existing health risks and worsening health problems (Kjellstrom & McMichael, 2015). Climate change leads to more frequent and intense extreme weather events, such as heavy rainfall, wildfires, heat waves, droughts, floods, and storms, exacerbating food- and water-borne diseases (Weilhammer et al., 2021). Temperature and humidity changes affect plant and insect distribution, influencing disease vectors like mosquitoes and ticks, potentially expanding vector-borne diseases introducing new species in new areas (Fischer et al., 2010; Semenza & Suk, 2018). Extreme heat increases the risk of various diseases, while socio-economic shifts induced by climate change may lead to adverse health outcomes, including via fuel poverty and food insecurity (Sanson et al., 2022). Rising global temperatures result in increased air pollution due to longer summers and shorter winters (Hodgson & Phillips, 2021). This heightened pollution, including ground-level ozone, stems from microbial growth and agricultural activities, with warmer temperatures trapping pollutants near the ground, especially in urban areas (Fiala et al., 2003; Ren et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2021; Jacob & Winner, 2009). Early pollen seasons exacerbate respiratory diseases and allergies, linked to climate-induced shifts in vegetation distribution (Beck et al., 2013; Rojo et al., 2021; Jato et al., 2013; Wayne et al., 2002).

Observed health effects

In recent decades, the deleterious health impacts of climate change on Europe's children and adolescents have emerged as a pressing concern within the public health domain. Manifestations of this phenomenon encompass a spectrum of challenges, each posing distinct risks to the physical and mental well-being of children. The increasing frequency and severity of heat waves across Europe have rendered children particularly vulnerable to conditions such as heat exhaustion and heatstroke (Kizer, 2020; Rossiello & Szema, 2019). Children born in 2020 will encounter a substantial rise in extreme occurrences, particularly heat waves, compared to those born in 1960, by potentially doubling the exposure levels (UNICEF, 2024). Moreover, the psychological toll of climate-related events on children and adolescents merits attention. Instances of extreme weather events and natural disasters engender psychological distress, manifesting as anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (Mambrey et al., 2019). Concomitant with rising temperatures is the exacerbation of air pollution, a phenomenon intricately linked to climate change. The respiratory systems of children, still undergoing development (D'Anci et al., 2006; Salvi et al., 2007), are uniquely susceptible to the detrimental effects of pollutants such as particulate matter and ozone (Beck et al., 2013). Between 2010 and 2019, an estimated 5,839 infants under one year succumbed to causes linked to air pollution in EU countries. In

2019, out of the 472 deaths among children and young individuals under 20 years old due to air pollution in the EU, the vast majority were infants under one year old (UNICEF, 2024).

Parallel to these trends is the expanding geographic range of vector-borne diseases, propelled by climatic shifts conducive to the proliferation of disease vectors. Lyme disease, once confined to specific regions, has disseminated across Europe, disproportionately affecting children engaged in outdoor activities (Kullbreg et al., 2020; Shapiro & Gerber, 2000).

Furthermore, climate change has amplified the risks of food- and water-borne diseases. Alterations in precipitation patterns and temperature have catalyzed shifts in microbial ecology, influencing the prevalence and distribution of pathogens in food and water sources. Water-borne diseases, such as cryptosporidiosis, giardiasis, and campylobacteriosis pose significant threats to child health. Campylobacteriosis have a reporting rate of 133.0 annual cases per 100,000 infants and children under 5 years old (ECDC- report campylobacteriosis). Floods, for instance, can compromise water quality, facilitating the transmission of water-borne pathogens and putting diarrheal disease as a leading cause of death in children (Griffiths, 2008).

Projected effects

Children are particularly vulnerable to the effects of climate change on their physical and mental health, both now and in the future (Bose O'Reilly et al., 2022). Central Europe is projected to experience significant warming, ranging from 1°C to over 4°C in the next 50 to 80 years (Hertig et al., 2023). Heat waves across Europe are expected to intensify, become more frequent, and last longer, with Southern Europe facing an increased risk of severe wildfires (Dupuy et al., 2020), ultimately putting children in greater risk. The increased temperature also affects expansion of arthropod vectors and the increasing occurrence of vector-borne diseases (Voyiatzaki et al., 2022). Projections also suggest an increase in extreme precipitation events, leading to more frequent and intense flooding (Myhre et al., 2019). Altered precipitation patterns may affect water- and food-borne disease transmission differently across regions (Ebi et al., 2018), and exacerbate diarrheal diseases. As discussed in the WHO, 2014 paper, the number of death due to diarrheal diseases are projected to increase in Europe for children aged under 15 years. Water scarcity will affect agricultural irrigation, and diminish crop yields, exacerbating food shortages and price spikes (Myers et al., 2017). Climate change significantly impacts crop production, potentially leading to declines in global yields of essential crops and influencing the micronutrient composition of various foods, posing additional challenges to food security (Nelson et al., 2010; Semba et al., 2022).

Annex II: Number of studies that found evidences for each health effects identified via the systematic review for each of the five categories of climate exposures

Extreme Weather		Pollen		Food Insecurity		Food- and Water-borne Diseases		Vector-borne Diseases	
Health Effects	#	Health Effects	#	Health Effects	#	Health Effects	#	Health Effects	#
respiratory diseases	26	asthma	13	obesity/overweight	23	E. coli infections (ETEC/STEC/VTEC)	19	dengue	10
mental health disorders	23	allergic rhinitis (ar)	5	undernutrition/malnutrition/micronutrient deficiencies	19	diarrhea	17	tick-borne encephalitis (human monocytic ehrlichiosis/japanese encephalitis/la crosse encephalitis/meningoencephalitis/chandipura viral encephalitis)	8
developmental disorders (cognitive/physical/ motoric/ behavioral/reproductive/emotional/ social/lingual/neurological/skeletal/ etc.)	21	allergic diseases, allergic respiratory diseases	3	developmental disorders (cognitive/physical/ behavioral/emotional/social/neurological/etc.)	14	salmonellosis	16	allergies/allergic rhinitis (AR)/food allergy (FA)	7
asthma, undernutrition/malnutrition/ micronutrient deficiencies/electrolyte imbalance	16	allergic rhinoconjunctivitis, atopic diseases, eosinophilic esophagitis, food allergy (fa), pollen food allergy syndrome (pfas), respiratory diseases	2	mental disorders	12	campylobacteriosis	12	lyme disease	5
allergic diseases (allergic respiratory diseases/allergic rhinitis (ar) /allergic rhinoconjunctivitis/allergic rhinosinusitis), cardiovascular diseases	13	anaphylaxis, cardiovascular diseases, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (copd), chronic rhinosinusitis (crs), eczema, eye infections, impaired fetal/neurological development, lower respiratory tract infections (lrti), pollionosis	1	stunting	7	enteric infections (bacterial/viral)	10	eczema	3

Extreme Weather		Pollen		Food Insecurity		Food- and Water-borne Diseases		Vector-borne Diseases	
Health Effects	#	Health Effects	#	Health Effects	#	Health Effects	#	Health Effects	#
infectious diseases	12			physical disorders	6	hepatitis a-e	9	alpha-gal syndrome, chikungunya, lyme neuroborreliosis, zika (microencephaly)	2
academic burnout, behavioral conditions, bronchiolitis, cancer, cardiopulmonary diseases, cerebrovascular diseases, chronic diseases, cryptosporidiosis, digestion disorders, dyspnea, measles, meningococcal meningitis, non-infectious diseases, parasitic diseases, plant diseases, pregnancy complications, pulmonary coccidioidomycosis, pulmonary fibrosis, rotavirus, sarcoidosis, shigellosis, sleeping disorders, stress, surgical diseases, typhoid fever, vector-borne disease, west nile fever, yellow fever	1			adverse childhood experiences, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (adhd), cardiometabolic risk, depression, gestational diabetes mellitus, kidney disease, metabolic disorders, negative emotional well-being, violence	1	acute kidney failure, asthma, bacillus/bacterial infections, bordetellosis, botulism, brachylaimidiasis, brucellosis, calicivirus, cholera, depression, diplostomidiasis, echinostomiasis, fasciolopsiasis, food-borne colitis, gastrodiscoidiasis, H. pylori infections, helminthiasis, hemolytic anemia, inpetigo, lecithodendriidiasis, leishmaniasis, leptospirosis, M. mucogenicum infection, measles, meningitis, meningoencephalitis, mental health disorders, metagonimiasis, microphallidiasis, microsporidiosis, nanophyetiasis, paramphistomatidiasis, perinatal infections, plagiorchiidiasis, plant diseases, pneumonia, post-traumatic stress disorder (ptsd), reactive arthritis syndrome (reiter's syndrome), respiratory diseases, scabies, septicemia, severe dehydrating illness, staphylococcus/ streptococcus infections, strigeidiasis, thrombocytopenia, trachoma, trematodiasis, tuberculosis	1	anaplasmosis, atopic dermatitis, cervical lymphadenopathy, congenital infection, dirofilariasis, ehrlichia-induced hlh, papular urticaria, rocky mountain spotted fever, spotted rickettsioses, thrombocytopenia syndrome, tick-borne relapsing fever, tularemia, visceral leishmaniasis, west nile virus-associated neuroinvasive disease, yellow fever	1

Annex III: Most researched risk factors as identified via the systematic review for the exposure category extreme weather effects

General terms related to climate change		Specific climate change-related extreme events		Secondary effects related to climate change		General variables as a proxy for climate change	
Terms	count	Terms	count	Terms	count	Terms	count
Extreme weather events, natural disasters	14	Extreme heat/high temperatures	28	Air pollution	23	Air temperature	7
Climate change	5	Floods	25	Food insecurity	9	Precipitation	3
Weather variability	2	Heat waves	20	Rising sea levels, water contamination, aeroallergens/longer pollen season	3	Humidity, seasonality, weather variability, wind speed	2
Climate-related hazards, weather-related disasters, global change	1	Wildfires	17	Increasing carbon dioxide levels, ozone depletion, water insecurity, chemical contamination	2	Salinity, sea surface temperatures, altitude, sunlight, water quality, desertification, frequency and intensity of extreme weather events	1
Storms	8	Droughts, Hurricanes	14	indoor/outdoor air pollution, indoor/outdoor molds, migration, water scarcity/stress	1		
Extreme precipitation, tsunamis	5						
Cyclones, tornados	3						
Typhoons	2						

Annex IV: Risk factors as identified via the systematic review for the exposure category food- and water-borne diseases

Terms	count
Food insecurity	46
Water insecurity	32
Poor sanitation	17
Contact with infected persons	12
Contact with domestic animals	11
Anti-microbial/multidrug resistance	7
Contact with pets, poor hygiene, soil contact	5
International trade, international travel, recreational water contact, toxic contamination, contaminated surfaces	4
Drinking raw milk, HIV infections	3
Contact with environment, exposure to farm environment, flooding, high population density, malnutrition	2
Aeroallergens, agricultural practices, air pollution, cancer, climate change, crawling, diabetes, experimental touching and testing behaviors, fishing, fossil fuel combustion, free-food markets, globalization, helminthiasis infections, immunodeficiency, inappropriate organic fertilizer usage, natural disasters, poor economic conditions, poor wastewater treatment, poverty, putting hands and objects in the mouth, reduced crop yields, reduced work capacity	1

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